

EFFECTS OF FIRM CHARACTERISTICS ON FINANCIAL REPORTING
QUALITY OF LISTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Financial reporting is one of the unique instruments of accounting reporting system that tries to provide necessary information for users to make economic and investment decisions on the evaluation of an economic enterprise's performance. Measuring and providing information that makes it possible to evaluate the past performance and effectively assess and predict the possible

future profitability and anticipated activities can be considered as a criterion for achieving this goal (Bolo, 2007).

Financial reporting quality includes the correctness of reported information to better describe a firm's operations. Practically, investors are really interested in information on firm's cash flow. This definition of financial reporting quality is in accordance with a definition proposed by the International Accounting Standards Board (2008); this board asserts that one of the objectives of financial reporting is to inform potential creditors and investors to make reasonable decisions and evaluate the expected cash of the firm. The main pointers of financial information quality from the perspective of the developers of accounting standards are relevance and reliability, which make information useful for decision makers (Hassas, 2006). Although the theoretical frameworks of financial accounting standards differ in terms of tendency toward reliability and relevance, they do not introduce a certain threshold for each of these two dimensions. It is possible that the relative preference between relevance and reliability vary between different groups of investors. For example, short-sighted investors will probably prefer relevance. Conversely, far-sighted investors will probably prioritize reliability (Sajjadi, Hossein-Zadeh, Ali, & Akghar, 2009).

Based on the theoretical framework issued by the Board, financial information should be firstly relevant and reliable to be useful in decision-makings. Relevant information should be timely gathered and provided. Furthermore, they must be predictable and feedback-contained. Reliability includes honesty, verifiability and impartiality (Zarif Fard, 2008).

The quality of financial reporting has always been an issue of interest among regulatory bodies, shareholders, researchers and the accounting profession itself. This is necessary because financial reporting has been a principal means of communicating financial information to outside users

(Johnson, Khurana & Reynolds, 2002). In addition to more efficient investment, quality financial reporting reduces information asymmetry between firm and financiers outside the firm. For example, quality financial reporting may force the firm to obtain positive net present value (NPV) in order to attract investors' capital. On the other hand, the financial reporting quality limits managers' motivations for engaging in activities that are of little or negative value. For instance, the financial reporting quality may facilitate better contracts to avoid investment inefficiency. Furthermore, it can increase investors' ability to control the investment decisions. Therefore, it is expected that quality financial reporting reduce excessive and wasting investments (Biddle, Hillary, & Verdi, 2009).

Three divergent views are debated globally in respect to firm characteristics and quality of financial reporting (Wallace, Naser & Mora, 1994; Chen & Jaggi, 2007). First, is that structure characteristics of firm play a prominent role in preventing managers from manipulating accounting numbers than other measures such as monitoring or performance variables. Second, others are of the opinion that monitoring mechanisms (independent directors and institutional shareholders) control better the opportunistic behaviour of management in preparing financial statements. The last view believes that performance variables surpass both structure and monitoring elements in checkmating the unethical accounting activities by managers, which reduces the quality of financial reporting.

The investigation of the effect of firms' characteristics on financial reporting quality represents one of the most systematic and sustained research efforts in the financial reporting literature. Cerf's (1961) inaugural empirical study of factors influencing the adequacy of United State corporate

annual report disclosure laid the foundation for a succession of studies conducted in numerous countries. The level of researchers' interest in this area directly reflects the impact that the adequacy of financial report quality has on decisions made by the various users of financial statements. It is upon this premise that this study is consummated. This of course is the crux of the matter.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The purpose of financial statements is to deliver useful information about the financial position, performance and changes in financial position of an entity that is valuable to a wide range of users in making economic and investment decisions. The statements prepared also show the results of the management's stewardship. In spite of the above, financial reporting quality in Nigeria remains weak compared to many advanced jurisdictions. This resulted in hampering of the growth of efficient equity markets. According to Shehu (2011), a common complaint among investors in Nigeria is that financial information on company's performance is either unavailable or, if provided, lacks credibility. Although complete lack of bias cannot be achieved, a certain level of accuracy is necessary for financial reporting information to be useful for investors' decision-making (International Accounting Standards Board, 2008).

Prior studies have shown that firm characteristics (structure, monitoring, and performance) influence the financial reporting quality of companies. Wallace, Naser and Mora (1994), Raffournier (1995), Oyelere, Laswad and Fisher (2003) observe that company specific determinants (liquidity, industry type, size, profitability and shareholder dispersion) influence the quality of financial reporting. Agency theory suggests that agents will increase disclosure to their

principals to reduce information asymmetry and thus, agency costs. In relation to this, Al-Shimmiri (2008) argue that the firms with higher debt in their capital structure are prone to higher agency costs; hence, they will be more likely to disclose additional information in order to reduce agency costs and information asymmetry with shareholders. Almilia and Surabaya (2009) assert that firms' specific characteristic is an important determinant of corporate disclosure.

Although, some considerable amount of literature exists on the interaction between firms characteristics and financial reporting quality in some countries', most notably the United States, Russia, Malaysia, Kenya and France (Njoroge, 2016; Samuel, Mudzamir & Mohammad, 2017; Titus, 2017; Ahmed, Maysam&Naim, 2018), however, the same is not true in economies like Nigeria where there is a relatively dearth in literature in this area, coupled with the huge institutional differences between Nigeria and other developed economies. A few of the available studies in Nigeria, such as Shehu and Ahmad (2013) investigate the association between firm characteristics and financial reporting quality in listed manufacturing firms. But, their study covers only a period of five years (2006-2010), which appears to be too short. More so, Uwalomwa, Uwuigbe and Okorie (2015), assess the effect of firm's characteristics on earnings management of listed companies, but considered only twenty listed firms and only cover a period of five years (2006-2010). John, Nkiru and luka (2017) examine the determinants of financial reporting quality but considered only listed agriculture and natural resources firms in Nigeria and the study utilized modified Jones model by Dechow (1995) to measure discretionary accruals. While, Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016) in their study on firm structural characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, they considered only banking industry of the economy, this therefore provide the gap this study filled

In order to close these existing gaps, and expand the frontier of knowledge in this area of study, this research work on firms' characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria utilized twenty-two firms (22) and covers the period of ten years (2007-2016). Thus, this study also used Jones model to calculate discretionary accruals, which other studies did not use.

In the light of previous studies' results, this study came to highlight the role that the structure, monitoring and performance can play in the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The need for such study is to bridge the gap in literature since these relationships have not been researched extensively in Nigeria. Moreover, Nigeria has witnessed many financial scandals that led many companies to go bankrupt such as Global Business, and Alshamyleh Gate. Thus, this study focuses on structure characteristics, monitoring characteristics and performance characteristics to determine their relationship with financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. To the best of knowledge of the researcher of this study, not much extant literature has looked at structure characteristics, monitoring characteristics and performance committee attributes jointly, to examine their relationship with financial reporting quality. This study therefore fills this gap by examining how structure characteristics attributes, monitoring characteristics and performance characteristics influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the objectives below, the following research questions are raised for this study;

- i. What is the effect of structure characteristic on the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange?
- ii. What is relationship between performance characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange?
- iii. What is the effect of monitoring characteristics on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine firms' characteristics with a view to determining its effect on financial reporting quality in listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of structure characteristics on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.
- ii. Examine the relationship between performance characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.
- iii. Examine the effect of monitoring characteristics on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

1.5 Statement of the Hypotheses

With due consideration to the research problems and questions, the following null hypotheses shall be tested in this study;

- H₀₁ Structure characteristics has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange
- H₀₂ Monitoring characteristics has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange
- H₀₃ Performance characteristics has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange

1.6 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study is based on the fact that it would make important contributions to knowledge. Firstly, the study provides empirical evidence of the relationship between firms' characteristics and financial reporting quality. As a result of this, managers of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria will be able to generate first-hand information on the effect firms' characteristics could have on financial reporting quality, for improved performance.

Secondly, this study will also enhance the theoretical and practical knowledge of the students and other researchers on the effect of firms' characteristics on financial reporting quality, and therefore serve as a reference material. Finally, it is believed that the findings of this research work will stimulate further research in this area of knowledge for theory building on the subject of firms' characteristics and financial reporting quality.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on firms' characteristics and the quality of financial reporting within the context of listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study covers the period

of ten (10) years, from 2008- 2017. Therefore, financial reporting quality proxy is represented by earnings quality by absolute discretionary accruals of the listed consumer goods companies during the period covered by the study.

The different dimensions of firms' characteristics, such as structure, monitoring, and performance was given due consideration. In this study, the researcher restricts the components of structure to firm's size and leverage; monitoring to board size and institutional shareholding; and performance to profitability and liquidity.

The independent variables that are used in this study is firm characteristics which is measured by using structure, monitoring and performance, whereas the dependent variable that is used in this study is financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies at Nigeria Stock Exchange. Dependent variable is measured by using proxy of earnings quality and it is measured by discretionary accruals (DAC) using Jones model, while the independent variables is measured by firms' size and leverage which are proxies for structure characteristics.

1.8 Definition of Terms

Firms' Characteristics: These fundamental qualities of a firm are capable of influencing the quality of financial reporting.

Financial Reporting Quality: The credibility of accounting information contained in a firm's financial report, which serves as an aid in decision-making.

Structure Characteristics: These refer to the corporate strategy, leverage, and size of the firm that are capable of influencing financial reporting quality.

Monitoring Characteristics: These are those variables that are used in monitoring the activities of managers so as to avoid their excesses. Such variable includes board composition, institutional shareholding, audit committee, etc.

Performance Characteristics: These refer to the performance variables of the firm such as sales, gross profit, and net profit earned for a certain period.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Firm Characteristics

In this study, the researcher grouped characteristics of firms that are related to the financial reporting quality into three; structure, monitoring, and performance characteristics.

Structural characteristic of the firm is the size and it is an attribute that affects financial reporting quality (Dechow & Ge, 2006). Firm size is measured in most cases by the asset size of the firm (Saheed, 2013). A large firm is expected to have a well-structured accounting and internal control department and should be able to engage the services of professionals so as to give credibility to the financial reporting process (Chalaki, Didar, & Riahezhad, 2012). They are equally likely to have a well-built information system that enables them track financial and non-financial information for operational, tactical and strategic purposes (Saheed, 2013). This is because a well-structured accounting and internal control department will ensure the integrity of financial report. Internal control procedures are meant to detect and prevent both the ability to manipulate earnings as well as mistakes or errors (Dechow & Ge, 2006).

More so, firm size is one of the most influential characteristics in organizational studies. Chen and Hambrick (1995) and Mintzberg (1979) explain the importance of firm size on financial reporting quality. Firm size has also been shown to be related to industry- sunk costs, concentration, vertical integration and overall industry profitability (Dean et al., 1998).

However, larger size companies are more likely to have more layers of management, greater number of departments, increased specialization of skills and functions, greater centralization and greater bureaucracy than smaller companies (Daft, 1995).

Recent research has found an association between firm size and inertia defined as slow adaptation to change or resistance to fundamental changes in conducting business (Miller and Chen, 1994). Inertia can be caused by constraints on action associated with firm age and size (Miller & Chen, 1994; Hannan & Freeman, 1984; Aldrich & Austen, 1986; Meyer & Zucker, 1989). Starbuck

(1985) assert that inertia can make change more costly and harder to achieve and maintain. Larger size companies may also find it more difficult to maintain an atmosphere of continuous change than smaller companies (Starbuck, 1985).

Firm leverage is the degree to which a company uses fixed-income securities, such as debt and preferred equity. With a high degree of financial leverage come high interest payments. The trade-off between agency costs of debt and equity (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Therefore, companies that are highly leveraged may be at risk of bankruptcy if they are unable to make payments on their debt, they may also be unable to find new lenders in the future. Leverage is not always bad, however; it can increase the shareholders' return on their investment and make good use of the tax advantages associated with borrowing.

Firm liquidity measures the company's ability to meet its short-term obligations using its liquid assets. It is usually measured by the current assets to current liabilities (current ratio).

2.1.2 Concept of Financial Reporting Quality

Over the years, the concept of financial reporting quality has raised serious concerns among financial market regulators, financial operators, investors and academic researchers; as reflected in the speech of the former U.S Security and Exchange Commission Chairman in 2002. More so, this concept has continued to receive attention due to the series of corporate failures in both developed and developing economies. This trend has invariably increased the doubts in the minds of stakeholders on the credibility and reliability of financial report.

The importance attached to accounting information by stakeholders of any given organization cannot be over emphasized; as the entire fate of the organization and its stakeholders depend on it. More so, accounting as a field also has a stake to protect, owing to the fact that earnings are the last product of the whole accounting process. Therefore, financial statements should always provide reliable information to assist users in decision-making. The statement should contain relevant, reliable, comparable and understandable information (Kamaruzaman, Mazlifa, & Maisarah, 2009). Reliability has to do with the quality of financial information that is reasonably free from error and bias and faithfully represents what it is intended to stand for. However, Johnson (2005) argues that an annual report can never be completely free from bias, since economic phenomena presented in annual reports are frequently measured under conditions of uncertainty. Many estimates and assumptions are included in the report. Accounting information is reliable to the extent that users can depend on it to judge the economic conditions or events that it purports to represent. However, reliability has the qualities of neutrality, representational, faithfulness and verifiability. Therefore, verifiability on the other hand means the ability through consensus among measurers to ensure that the information is correct or that the chosen method of measurement has been used without error or bias. It has three key aspects namely; consensus among observers, assurance of correspondence to economic events, and direct and indirect verification (Johnson, 2005). For financial statement to be understood clearly, the presentation should not be misleading or ambiguous. Users should be able to understand the information presented without undue effort (International Accounting Standard Board, 2008).

In most developing economies and in spite of the various governance structures and frameworks established by most countries, cases of corporate malpractices remain prevalent. This is also the

case in Nigeria where despite the publication of a new corporate governance code in 2003 and 2011 by Securities and Exchange Commission; cases of misappropriation of fund and falsification of reports to suit management interest has continued unabatedly. Hence, this study adds to the body of existing knowledge by assessing the relationship between firms' characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed companies in Nigeria. Managers can use their control over the firm to achieve personal objectives at the expense of stakeholders (Uwuigbe, Fagbemi & Anusien, 2012; Uwuigbe, 2013). In this regard, Kang and Kim (2011) opine that management could influence reported earnings by making accounting choices or by making operating decisions discretionally.

Quality of financial reporting is to accurately report information to better explain the company's operations in practice, information on company cash flow that is of interest to investors. In defining the quality of financial reporting, the International Accounting Standards Board (2008) as cited by Biddle, Rodrigo and Verdi (2009) state that one of the objectives of financial reporting is to inform creditors and potential investors so as to help them in reasonable decision-making and evaluation of the company's expected cash flow. Financial reporting quality is an important issue that attracts the attention of managers, investors and shareholders, while the task of managers is to improve the quality of financial reporting. Companies that have the potential of strategy and corporate governance, quality financial report will be experience by Companies where strong governance and strategies are used, leading to improved quality of financial reporting and the resulting performance can be increased. On the other hand, companies that do not have such a strategy, of course, improving quality of financial reporting and the value of such companies are therefore uncertain because company's strategy often spurs good company's financial reporting quality.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Structure Characteristics of the Firm and Financial Reporting Quality

A structural characteristic of the firm is the size and it is an attribute that affects financial reporting quality (Dechow & Ge, 2006). Firm size is measured in most cases by the asset size of the firm (Saheed, 2013). A large firm is expected to have a well-structured accounting and internal control department and should be able to engage the services of professionals so as to give credibility to the financial reporting process (Chalaki, Didar & Riahnezhad, 2012). They are equally likely to have a well-built information system that enables them track all financial and non-financial information for operational, tactical and strategic purposes (Saheed, 2013). This is because a well-structured accounting and internal control department will ensure the integrity of financial report. Internal control procedures are meant to detect and prevent both the ability to manipulate earnings as well as mistakes or errors (Dechow & Ge, 2006). The study period is too short to make a short term plan and this current study period covers 10years which is from 2008 to 2017.

Waweru and Riro (2013) investigate the influence of corporate governance and firm specific characteristics on earnings management. The study found that company size is not significantly related to financial reporting quality, this is consistently related with the result obtained by (Missonier-Piera, 2004). While, Thoopsamut and Jaikengkit (2009) investigate the economic choices of accounting method in Swiss and the result obtained and also accept the assertion that company size is not a significant variable in determinant of financial reporting quality. The study was carried out in Swiss while this current study is in Nigerian, also, this current study will be updated to 2017, and this makes this study current.

In line with the above argument, a contrary finding by Waweru and Riro (2013) assert that company size is a major factor shaping Managers choices of accounting in Japan. This study relevance is only in Japan and cannot be applicable in Nigeria. Moreover, Shehu and Ahmad (2013) document that firm size has significant effect on earnings quality. The study argued that large consumer goods firms in Nigeria tend to report more reliable and qualitative information in their financial report than small ones. According to the study, the reason for this is as a result of strong internal control system, governance mechanisms, and ability to access high quality service from large audit firms. The combination of these factors should discourage earnings management, which is expected to improve the quality of financial reporting. While the study dependent variable is earnings quality, this present study focuses on financial reporting quality.

However, Huang, Rose-Green and Lee (2012) while studying CEO age and financial reporting quality, using the meeting and beating of analyst earnings forecasts and financial restatements as a proxy for financial reporting quality, a sample of 3,413 firms for a period 2005 to 2008 and using tools of regression analysis in analysing the variables found that firm size is significant and negatively related to financial reporting quality. The study period is too short to make a short-term plan and this current study period is ten (10).

Firm size will also affect the corporate governance characteristics as well as the level of earnings management (Becker, DeFond, Jimbalvo & Subramanyam, 1998). Besides, Shehu and Ahmad (2013) posit that large firms have strong reasons to manipulate their earnings in order to keep consistent earnings growth trend, meet and beat earnings expectations. Although, Missioner-Piera (2004) and Thoopsamut and Jaikengkit (2009) contrary to Shehu and Ahmad's findings in which

they posit that company size is not significantly related to financial reporting quality, although their work was not conducted in an emerging economy. The reason for this divergent result could be the level of development of the economies in which the studies were conducted. If firm size is likely to affect the corporate governance characteristics as posited by (Becker, DeFond, Jiambalvo, & Subramanyam, 1998) it is likely it will equally affect the level of financial reporting quality. The study is restricted to one corporate governance characteristic, while this study used firm characteristics.

Moreover, one important structural variable is the size of the firm. Studies carried out by a group of researchers showed that the size of the firm has a positive effect on financial reporting and some of the reasons are considered as establishment of an effective internal control system, the relationship with great auditory institutions and observing the cost of creditability and reputation. Cohen (2004) finds a positive relationship between size of the company and financial reporting quality. Larger firms are able to afford a well-structured internal control system, or engage services of one of the top auditing firms for the audit of its financial statement, which is expected to enhance the quality of their financial report

Again, another structural characteristic is the firm's leverage. Hung and Song (2006) investigate 1,200 Chinese companies within the period of 1994 to 2003 and their studies shows that leverage in Chinese companies is directly related to the variable of size of company and fixed assets but it is inversely related to profitability, development opportunities and managerial ownership. The study is only useful in Chinese and cannot be used for policy making in Nigeria, also, the study stopped at 2003, there is need to examine the current effect of firm characteristics on financial

reporting quality in Nigeria. Shehu (2012) investigates the effect of features of company on the quality of financial reporting of productive companies in Nigeria. The study found out that liquidity has an inverse and significant relationship on the earning quality, but the other features of size of the company, leverage, the combination of board of directors, institutional stockholders, profitability and growth of the company had a significant and positive effect on the quality of financial report of studied Nigerian productive companies. Although, a large firm can be motivated to engage in earnings management in order to maintain certain level of profile (Waweru & Riro, 2013), this will also affect the financial reporting quality. This study focuses on consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

John, Nkiru and Luka (2017) investigate the determinants of financial reporting quality in listed Agriculture and Natural Resources firms in Nigeria. The sectors comprise of 9 listed Agriculture and Natural Resources Firms, made up of 5 Agriculture and 4 Natural Resources firms. A sample of 7 firms was drawn from the population. Data was collected through secondary sources from annual financial reports of the firms from 2008-2015. The study adopted the correlation and ex-post factor research designs and employed the use regression as a tool for data analysis. The results showed a positive significant relationship between leverage, liquidity, board size and financial reporting quality, measured using residuals from the modified Jones model by Dechow, et al. (1995). It is recommended among others that managers of firms in the Agriculture and Natural Resources sectors maintain an optimum liquidity level and finance their operations from more of debt instruments, so as to ensure quality of reported accounting numbers. The study findings is restricted to agriculture and natural resources companies and cannot be used in consumer goods companies Nigeria.

Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016) examine firm structural characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study used secondary data from the published reports of thirteen listed deposit money banks in Nigeria for over a period of ten years between 2005 and 2014. The study developed a model for loan loss provisions and generated the residuals, using these residuals known as abnormal loan loss provisions as the dependent variable for the multiple regression analysis, the study did not find any evidence of significant relationship between firm age, size, leverage and financial reporting quality. The finding in this study revealed that there is a negative relationship between firm size and financial reporting quality, the relationship is quite insignificant. The implication of this to the regulators and other stakeholders is for them to now focus on other characteristics that are significantly related to financial reporting quality. The study centered on deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange market while this current study is on listed consumer goods companies.

2.2.2 Monitoring Characteristics of the Firm and Financial Reporting Quality

Recent literature documents that institutional investors have different incentives to monitor managers depending on the investment scope. Liu and Peng (2008) and Chen and Jaggi (2008) observe that independent long term investors with substantial ownership effectively monitor merger and acquisition decisions, while short-term investors give managers the latitude to achieve value-decreasing mergers and acquisitions. In this regard Liu and Peng (2008) note that dedicated institutions who are more interested in long term returns have stronger incentives to monitor managers than their transient counterpart. Empirical research supports this idea (Hartzell & Starks, 2003; Holderness, 2003; Jiambalvo, Rajgopal, & Venkatachalam, 2002; McConnell & Servaes,

1990). Given their large financial stake, institutional investors have incentives, resources, and the ability to monitor a firm's stakeholder policy. Recent research also indicates that the existence of stronger shareholders may improve internal control, and thus may be an effective monitoring device for improving financial reporting quality. To the extent that an appropriate power-sharing relationship between shareholders and managers reduces the moral hazard problems that lower overall firm value and allow shareholders to effectively monitor the financial reporting practice. These studies are not carried out in Nigeria there it cannot be used in decision making in Nigeria.

Institutional investor is an endogenous governance variable that has been central in corporate governance discussions. The argument to categorize it as an endogenous mechanism is supported by the fact that corporate disclosure, together with firm characteristics such as size, financial performance, and risk may affect institutional ownership and accruals quality simultaneously (Liu & Peng, 2008). Prior literatures have acknowledged that institutional presence can serve as an effective monitoring mechanism in the firm (e.g. Bowen, Rajgopal & Vankatachalam, 2003; Shehu, 2011). Institutions are particularly important in corporate governance discussions because, in many cases, they hold a substantial proportion of total equity shares of a good number of firms and are thus relevant to policy makers. It is therefore quite possible that these institutions have an effect on firm performance as well as the discretionary behaviour of managers. Perhaps, the predominant view is that institutions have the required resources and financial expertise to monitor and discipline managers and thereby reducing agency problems (Schleifer & Vishney, 1997: Roodposhti & Chashmi, 2011). However, it can be argued that if institutions hold a large amount of equity shares of company, that in itself may exert an enormous pressure on the part of managers

to manipulate earnings in order to please these institutions. These studies are old in their period and this study will extend its study period to 2017, which make it current.

Another monitoring variables examined in the study is ownership concentration, which is also referred to as block holders. It is the proportion of shares (usually more than 5%) owned by a certain percentage of shareholders. It is argued that the higher the number of shares owned by the block holders, the more the pressure on managers to act in conformity with those shareholders' interest (Sanda, Mukaila, & Garba, 2005). Large ownership concentration has more incentives to manage earnings because the expected benefit from equity holding in the firm outweighs the cost associated with monitoring managers (Ramsey & Blair 1993). If this is true, then we expect ownership concentration to be inversely related to earnings management and hence reporting quality. However, some researchers observe that high ownership concentration beyond a certain level may lead to abuse of power, which could be detrimental to the value maximization goal of the firm (Sanda, Mukaila, & Garba, 2005). These studies are old in their period and this study will extend the study period to 2017, which make it current.

Studies on the relationship between ownership concentration and financial reporting quality also have yielded inconsistent results. Roodposhti and Chashmi (2010) find a negative relationship between ownership concentration and earning management, when they used 196 firms listed on Tehran Stock Exchange as their sample for the period between 2004-2008, to examine the effect of board composition and ownership concentration on earnings management. The study period is too short to make a short-term decision, while this study period is ten (10) years. In the same vein, Klai and Omri (2011) investigate the impact of corporate governance on financial reporting quality in Tunisia. The study used 22 listed firms between the periods of 1997-2007. They find that

ownership concentration is negatively associated with earnings management. The study is only useful in Tunisia and cannot be used for policy making in Nigeria, also, the study stopped at 2007, there is need to examine the current effect of firm characteristics on financial reporting quality in Nigeria.

Conversely, using top 200 listed non-financial companies, Hashim and Devi (2008) examine the association between board independence, CEO duality and accruals management. They find that ownership concentration is associated with high income-increasing earnings management. Besides the exclusion of financial firms from all the studies mentioned above and economic differences of nation's calls for an investigation of similar problems in an economy like ours. The study focused on non-financial companies while this study focuses on consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Devi and Aishah (2009) examine the relationship between internal monitoring mechanisms namely the role of board independence and the ownership structure (managerial ownership, family ownership and institutional ownership) and the financial reported earnings quality. Using data from 280 non-financial companies listed on Bursa Malaysia's Main Board for the year 2004, this study fails to find any significant evidence on the relationship between the traditional functions of board of director's composition (i.e. proportion of independent non-executive directors) and earnings quality measured by accrual quality model. However, this study found positive significant associations between proportion of family members and earnings quality, which suggest that concentrated shareholdings in family ownership have incentives to reduce agency costs through a better alignment of shareholder and managerial interests. Given the growing role of institutional shareholder in Malaysian capital market, it is interesting to note that this study find positive

significant evidence on the relationship between institutional ownership and earnings quality. Concentrated shareholdings by institutional investors provide an incentive for diligent monitoring as they have the resources, expertise and stronger incentives to actively monitor the actions of management and improve financial reported earnings. The study is limited to the Malaysia alone; it cannot be applied in Nigeria.

Managerial ownership represents the interest of managers in the equity shareholding of a firm. The reason behind the rise of this corporate governance variable is rooted in the agency theory, which assumes that managers' equity holdings encourages them to act in a way that maximizes the value of the firm. Warfield, Wild, and Wild (1995) suggest that the interest of both shareholders and management starts to converge as the management holds a portion of the firm's equity ownership. This implies that the need for intense monitoring by the board should decrease (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Studies on the interaction between managerial shareholding and earnings management have revealed inconclusive results. Yeo, Yann-Ching and Yi-Mien (2003) examine the relationship between managerial ownership, audit quality and earnings management, using a sample consisting of 490 firm-year observations drawn from the firms listed on the Stock Exchange of Singapore for the period between 1990-1992. Their findings suggest that when management ownership is less than or equal to 25%, managers' opportunistic behaviour is reduced. However, as it crosses 25%, management ownership is positively related with aggressive income-increasing discretionary accruals. The study is only useful in Singapore and cannot be used for policy implication in Nigeria because of difference in political and socio-economic environment.

Similarly, Johari, Saleh, Jaffar and Hassan (2008) investigate the impact of board independence, competency and ownership on earnings management. Using a sample of 224 firms listed on Malaysia Stock Exchange and employing different accruals estimation models; they find that management ownership is positively related with discretionary accruals in all models. This suggests that the higher the ownership of a firm's shares by its managers, the more the presence of earnings manipulation. The study is only useful in Malaysia and cannot be used for policy implication in Nigeria because of difference in political and socio-economic environment. Monks and Minow (2011) and Lipton and Lorsch (1992) state that larger boards are able to commit more time and effort, whereas smaller boards are able to commit less time and effort, to overseeing management. Klein (2002b) extends this argument by saying that board monitoring is positively associated with larger boards because of their ability to distribute the workload to many people. The study is restricted to one corporate governance characteristic, while this study used firm characteristics.

One of the most important factors influencing the integrity of the financial accounting process involves the board of directors, whose responsibility is to provide independent oversight of management performance and to hold management accountable to shareholders for its actions (DeFond & Jiambalvo, 1994; Dichev & Skinner, 2002). Prior research examining the association between the corporate governance mechanisms concerning the board of directors (e.g. independence of board or board size, expertise of directors or board members, and stock ownership of board members) and the extent of earnings manipulation finds inconclusive results. While the empirical results concerning board attributes are mixed due to different research designs and empirical settings, a general belief is that boards are more effective in their monitoring of

management when there is a strong base of independent directors on the board (Beasley, 1996; Peasnell, Pope & Young, 2000; Klein, 2002; Xie, Davidson & Dadalt, 2003). These studies are old in their period and this study will extend the study period to 2017, which make it current.

Institutional shareholders also serve a monitoring role in mitigating opportunistic behaviour of managers (Edwards & Hubbard, 2000). Empirical research supports this idea (McConnell & Servaes, 1990; Jiambalvo, Rajgopal, & Venkatachalam, 2002; Hartzell & Starks, 2003; Holderness, 2003). Recent research also indicates that existence of stronger shareholders may improve internal control, and thus may be an effective monitoring device for improving financial reporting quality. An appropriate power-sharing relationship between shareholders and managers reduces the moral hazard problems that lower overall firm value and allow shareholders to effectively monitor the financial reporting practice. These studies are old in their period and this study will extend the study period to 2017, which makes it current.

A study on firm's characteristics as determinants of financial reporting quality documented that larger independent board membership and larger institutional and block shareholding as well as managerial shareholdings are associated with lesser earnings management (Farber, 2005). Corporate monitoring by these variables can constrain managers' behaviour. Large institutional investors have the opportunity, resources, and ability to monitor, discipline and influence managers. These studies are old in their period and this study will extend the study period to 2017, which make it current.

Shehu (2013) examines monitoring characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed manufacturing firms in Nigerian. Financial reporting quality is represented with earnings management using the modified Dechow and Dichev's (2002) model. Using 32 firms-years longitudinal panelled of 160 observations, panel OLS is estimated and controlled for fixed/random effects. The result shows a significant positive relationship between monitoring characteristics and financial reporting quality. The Hausman specification test shows that the panel result after controlling for random, best suits the population as the fixed effect hypothesis was rejected by the Wald/Ch2 test. The control variables both returns on assets and return on equity are significant. Leverage, independent directors, audit committee, institutional, block and managerial shareholdings are all significant implying monitoring characteristics is influencing financial reporting quality of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study used only monitoring which is one of the attributes of firm characteristics while this study used three of the attributes of firm characteristics which are structure, monitoring and performance characteristics and this study extends the period to 2017, which makes it current.

Samuel, Mudzamir and Mohammad (2017) examine the relationship of audit committee size and financial reporting quality in Nigeria. The empirical study used a sample of 189 companies and 664 year observation from the period of 2011-2015. One of the desirable features of corporate governance is to enhance financial reporting quality for facilitating efficient and effective resources allocation of economic decision making by corporate managers. Panel data regression was adopted and audit committee size was found positive and significant with financial reporting quality. The study results underscore the importance of the corporate governance recommendation as a mean of strengthening the monitoring and oversight role of audit committee plays in the

financial reporting process. The study is limited by its study period while this study extends to 2017, which makes it current.

2.2.3 Performance Characteristics of the Firm and Financial Reporting Quality

The study used performance variables as control variables without transformation, which could give a different result if used as continuous variable in the model. The level of leverage has also been argued by past researchers to have an influence on financial reporting quality. In terms of the level of disclosure, Alsaeed (2006) argues that higher debt firms have higher agency costs and therefore need to have more information disclosed in order to satisfy the needs of creditors for information. A study by Craig and Diga (1998) find a significant positive relationship between debt ratio and level of disclosure, while Alsaeed (2006) fail to find it significant, whereby it was argue that this was probably due to the fact that the creditors may have shared private information with their debtors. In contrast, higher leveraged company is argued to have higher bankruptcy risk, which in turn will lead to litigation risk (Rahman& Ali, 2006) and thus, increase management's tendency to manipulate firm's financial reporting to overcome this risk. This has been supported by findings by Klein (2002b) which showed that a company's leverage is significantly positively related to the level of abnormal accruals. Moreover, a study by Davidson, Stewart and Kent (2005) had also found a significant positive relationship between leverage and discretionary accruals. However, a subsequent study by Rahman and Ali (2006) and Yang and Krishnan (2005) did not document any significant relationship between company leverage and accruals. These studies stopped in 2006 and this study will extend the study period to 2017, which make it current.

Firms' profitability has also been argued to have an influence on the quality of financial reporting. Alsaeed (2006) argue that a profitable firm may feel proud of its achievements and therefore would

wish to disclose more information to the public in order to promote positive impressions of its performance. However, even though a study by Haniffa and Cooke (2002) did find a significant positive relationship between return on equity (ROE) and voluntary disclosure. A study by Alsaeed (2006) on the other hand, find insignificant relationships. Besides that, the level of profit has also been argued to have an influence on the manipulation of accounting accruals because managers may manage earnings to increase their bonus rewards (Yang & Krishnan, 2005). However, Yang and Krishnan (2005) and Rahman and Ali (2006) did not find any significant relationships between the level of net income and discretionary accruals. This inconsistency and insignificance in the results is probably due to the use of current profitability, instead of changes in profits. Therefore, studies by Klein (2002b) and Davidson, Stewart and Kent (2005) assert that the changes in profit influence the manipulation of accounting accruals. Both studies have found support for this argument. Their studies indicate a significant positive relationship between changes in net income and accruals in financial accounts. Several studies suggest that small profits are not evidence of earnings management. Dechow, Richardson, and Tuna (2003) in a large-sample study, find no relation between realizations of small profits and increases in discretionary accruals. Beaver, McNichols, and Nelson (2007) suggest that asymmetric taxes, rather than opportunistic choices, can explain the kink. Durtschi and Easton (2005) suggest that the kink is due to statistical and sample bias issues. These studies data stopped in 2007 while this study will extend to 2017, which makes it current.

Nwaobia, Kwarbai, Jayeoba and Ayibade (2016) state that financial reporting quality has been said to play an important role in reducing information asymmetry. The study sample consists of 10 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange Market and the study period is 5 years (2010-2014). Data on accrual quality, volume of investment, Size, age and growth rate and

earnings per share were drawn from the published annual report and accounts of the sampled companies. Correlation matrix, Vector auto regressive estimation and Pooled OLS model were employed for the analysis. Diagnostic tests for post estimation were also performed on the model. The result of the Ramsey Reset test shows a p-value of 0.2105, implying that model has no omitted variables. Also, Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data indicates no first-order autocorrelation, showing a p-value of 0.3642. The study measured accruals quality based on the modified accrual model proposed by Mac Nichols in 2002. The study finds evidence of a positive association between investors' decision and financial reporting quality. The study is limited to ten manufacturing companies in Nigeria and the study period is too short, cannot be used for short-term decision, while this current study used all the twenty-two consumer goods companies in Nigeria and this study period covers ten years (2008 – 2017) which makes it current.

Njoroge (2016) examines the impact of financial reporting quality on the subsequent cash flows of firms listed at the Nairobi securities exchange by exploring the effects of relevance, reliability, understandability and comparability as the indicators of financial reporting quality. The research considered financial statements from firms listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE) for the period between 2011 and 2015. The study adopted descriptive research design to obtain factual, accurate and systematic data. The results showed that financial reporting quality affects subsequent cash flows to a low degree of 23.1% while 76.9% of the influence is caused by other variables. Similarly, it was established that relevance and reliability have a significant relationship with cash flows while understandability and comparability were found to be insignificant. The study is limited to Kenya and cannot be applied in Nigeria.

Joseph and Ahmed (2017) investigate corporate governance and financial reporting quality in Nigeria. The research used a sample of 40 companies listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE)

from 2006 to 2015. The relationship between corporate governance mechanisms (board characteristics, audit committees, board independence, board size and growth) and financial reporting quality was observed. The results of the multiple regression analysis were statistically significant at 0.05 level. The F statistics of 3.641 shows that the results typically explained the model. The findings of the study revealed that corporate governance improves the financial reporting quality in Nigeria. The study stopped in 2015, while this study extends to 2017, which make it current.

Ezelibe, Nwosu and Orazulike (2017) investigate impact of corporate governance on the financial reporting quality of quoted companies in Nigeria. Fifteen firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange market under the consumer goods sector with updated financial information for the period under study were selected and analysed for the study. Data for the study were extracted from corporate annual reports and accounts of selected firms for the period 2012-2016. Corporate governance proxied by board size and audit committee independence and financial reporting quality was represented by audit delay. The study adopted simple regression techniques for the quoted sampled firms analyzed. The findings revealed that audit committee independence does not exert significant effect on audit delay of corporate firms. Also, board size has a significant negative relationship with audit delay of corporate firms in Nigeria. Consequent upon this study, it was recommended that corporate policies should reflect commitment to company variables such as board size that will significantly affect the quality of financial reporting. This position is borne out of the preponderance of the negative relationship between board size and audit delay. The study stopped in 2016 and utilized simple regression analysis while this study applied multiple regression analysis and extends to 2017, which make it current.

Ahmed, Maysam and Naim (2018) examine empirically the relationship between the quality of financial reporting and non-financial business performance in public listed companies in Jordan. The data for the research were collected through self-administrated questionnaire of 239 respondents from public listed companies in Stock Amman Market database (2017). The results showed that the components of the quality of financial reporting are significantly influence by non-financial business performance and the variations of the quality of financial reporting among these companies were significantly found to be related to their size and experience and not to their type of business, which they belong to. The study is restricted to Jordan, it used primary data, while this study used secondary data, and it cannot be used in Nigeria.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Efficient Contracting Theory

Efficient contracting theory studies the role of financial accounting information in moderating information asymmetry between contracting parties, thereby contributing to efficient contracting and stewardship and efficient corporate governance. Information asymmetry arises in contracting since management possesses insider information about the state of the firm, and may not necessarily share this with other contracting parties or, if they do share, may distort or exaggerate the information. Also, management's effort in operating the firm is not directly observable by outsiders. In both cases, outside contracting parties look to accounting information to help protect themselves from exploitation. Corporate governance is defines as those policies that align the firm's activities with the interests of its investors and society. Efficient contracting is an important component of this alignment. Firms enter into many contracts, such as with customers, suppliers, management, other employees, and lenders. For good corporate governance, these contracts should be efficient. That is, they must attain an optimal trade-off between the benefits and costs of

contracting. For example, a firm may benefit from lower borrowing costs if it incurs costs to reassure lenders, such as pledging specific assets as security, or accepting a covenant to limit further borrowing, which would water down the security of existing lenders.

Contracting is relevant to financial accounting since important contracts depend on accounting variables. Thus, debt contracts may contain covenants, such as maintaining a specified level of working capital, not exceeding a specified debt–equity ratio, or maintaining an agreed times interest earned ratio. Also, bonuses paid under managerial compensation contracts typically depend on net income, both directly and indirectly through the effect of reported earnings on share price.

The theory assumes that managers, like investors, are rational. As a result, managers cannot be assumed necessarily to maximize firm profits and, more generally, act in the best interests of investors. Rather, they will do so only if they perceive such behavior to be in their own interests. Consequently, the interests of managers, lenders, and shareholders conflict. Efficient contracting theory studies how this conflict is resolved. In particular, it predicts how managers will react to new accounting standards, it helps us to understand why managers often object to new standards and, through better understanding, it enables us to appreciate how efficient contract design can help to align the interests of managers with those of lenders and shareholders.

2.3.2 Opportunist Theory

The opportunistic perspective holds the view that managers, who are agents to the principal, act to their self-interests. They only adopt accounting policies that allow them to gain, in the view that

the firm also gains. Different types of hypothesis exist such as political cost, bonus plan and debt hypothesis that show what motives make the managers choose one accounting method over another.

- i. **Management Compensation Hypothesis (Bonus Plan Hypothesis):** The management compensation hypothesis states that managers who have accounting incentives or their remuneration that is tied up with the firm's accounting performance will tend to manipulate accounting method and figures to show the accounting performance better than it should be. Such as managers electing to use different depreciation method and allowing lower profits at the start and higher profits towards the end. Older managers will tend to ignore any research and development costs because it will lower current year profits affecting their income.
- ii. **Debt-Equity Hypothesis:** The debt/equity hypothesis states that managers will tend to show better profits as similar to the bonus plan in the intention of having a better performance and liquidity position to pay the interest and principal of the debt they have accumulated in the business. The higher the debt/equity level the more likely it is that the managers will tend to use accounting methods and procedures in increasing accounting profit.
- iii. **Political Cost Hypothesis:** The political cost hypothesis assumes that firms will tend to show their profits lower by using different accounting methods and procedures so that the firm does not attract the attention of politicians, who will have an eye on high profit industries. Allowing lower profits steers away any attention by the public and the eyes of the government who will place higher regulation on high earning firms.

In this study, the opportunist theory is selected to link structure variables with financial reporting quality and agency theory to frame monitoring variables with financial reporting quality, while the

financial reporting quality and performance variables will be anchored on efficient contracting theory. However, the structure variables, monitoring variables and performance variables form firm characteristics that represent the explanatory variables of the study.

2.3.3 Agency Theory

The agency theory assumes that there is an imaginary contract between the managers of a firm and its shareholders. The managers are labelled as the ‘agents’. They perform their tasks and run the firm on behalf of the ‘principal’, the firm’s shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). So according to this theory, managers are expected to act according to the will of the shareholders. However, the agency theory points out that this is often not the case, as the two groups might have different interests. This is called the ‘principal-agent problem’.

The principal-agent problem consists of two central problems: self-interest and information asymmetry. When the interests of management are not aligned with the interests of the shareholders, management might follow a strategy in order to maximize its own wealth at the cost of the returns to the shareholders. Information asymmetry exists when managers have more information than shareholders do. This way, it is difficult for the shareholders to ensure that management is acting in line with the shareholders’ interests.

In order to reduce management’s self-interest and information asymmetry, agency costs have to be incurred. Agency costs are composed of monitoring costs, bonding costs and residual loss. The former is the cost of shareholders monitoring managers’ activities. Bonding costs are paid by the agents to assure the principal that their actions will not negatively affect shareholder value.

Residual loss is the difference between management's choices and the decisions that would have led to shareholder welfare maximization (Shehata, 2014).

Moreover, there are costs of risks and rewards. Suppose that the interests of managers and shareholders are perfectly aligned, in that case, managers make decisions with the purpose to maximize shareholder value. Many firms apply an incentive system for managers. When shareholder value rises, manager compensation increases. Therefore, when managers' decisions turn out to be profitable, there are costs of reward for the firm, as manager compensation increases. However, there is always the risk that management makes the wrong choices. In that case, shareholder value declines. This is called the cost of risks.

The agency theory advocates that the independent of directors and institutional shareholding have a positive association with good earnings quality.

2.4 Summary

In this chapter, the researcher reviewed and presented relevant literature of firm characteristics and financial reporting quality. The chapter started with the presentation of conceptual framework of the study and then followed by firm characteristics as grouped by the researcher into structure, monitoring and performance.

In order to close the existing gaps in the literature viewed, and expand the frontier of knowledge in this area of study, this research work on firms' characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria utilized twenty-two firms (22) and covers the period

of ten years (2008-2017). Thus, this study also used Jones model to calculate discretionary accruals, which other studies did not use.

In the light of previous studies' results, this study came to highlight the role that the structure, monitoring and performance can play in the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The need for such study is to bridge the gap in literature since these relationships have not been researched extensively in Nigeria. Moreover, Nigeria has witnessed many financial scandals that led many companies to go bankrupt such as Global Business, and Alshamyleh Gate. Thus, this study focuses on structure characteristics, monitoring characteristics and performance characteristics to determine their relationship with financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. To the best of knowledge of the researcher of this study, not much extant literature has looked at structure characteristics, monitoring characteristics and performance committee attributes jointly, to examine their relationship with financial reporting quality. This study therefore fills this gap by examining how structure characteristics attributes, monitoring characteristics attributes and performance characteristics attributes influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The chapter ended with the discussion of theoretical framework and those specifically underpinning the study.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts descriptive research design to investigate the relationships as well as the effects of firm characteristics on the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies on

the Nigerian Stock Exchange. This design is chosen because of its effectiveness in assessing the relationships and the effects of two or more variables (that is, the dependent and independent variables).

The study is designed in two stages. First part is the measure of financial reporting quality by using modified Jones model of estimating discretionary accruals. While, the second part shall be the estimation of the effects of firm characteristics (that is structure, monitoring and Performance) on financial reporting quality.

3.2 Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

The population of this study consists of all listed Consumer goods companies on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) over the ten years (2008-2017) period. Information available to the researcher from the Nigerian Stock Exchange Fact book of 2017 revealed a total of twenty two (22) Consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The list of twenty two (22) consumer goods companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange considered for this study is listed below:

S/N	Name of Companies
1	7up Bottling Company Plc
2	Cadbury Nig. Plc
3	Champion Brew. Plc

4	Dangote Flour Mills Plc
5	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc
6	Dn Tyre & Rubber Plc
7	Flour Mills Nig. Plc
8	Golden Guinea Brew. Plc
9	Guinness Nig. Plc
10	Honey Well Flour Mill Plc
11	International Brew. Plc
12	McNichols Plc
13	Multi-Trex Integrated Foods Plc
14	Nig. Flour Mills Plc
15	Nascon Allied industries Plc
16	Nestle Nig. Plc
17	Nigeria Brew Plc
18	Nigeria Enamelware Plc
19	PZ Cussons Nig. Plc
20	Unilever Nig. Plc
21	Union Dicon Salt Plc
22	Vita foam NigPlc

Source: Nigerian Stock Exchange

The table above shows the twenty two (22) listed consumer goods companies available on the NSE, are the population of this study, and since they are not too many, this study utilized all of them as sample of the study.

3.3 Methods of Data Collection

For the purpose of this study, secondary data were exploited from the financial statements of the sampled listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange under consideration within the period (2008-2017). The use of secondary data in this study is justified based on the fact that the study is based on quantitative research methodology and hence requires quantitative data.

3.4 Technique for Data Analysis and Model Specification

The study adopts the use of both descriptive statistics and panel regression for the listed sampled consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange in the estimation of the regression equation under consideration. Descriptive data for the dependent and independent variables generated in this study are analysed using the mean scores.

While inferential analysis entails bivariate and multivariate analyses, which are used in hypotheses testing. The null hypotheses stated in this study were tested at 5% level of significance using both the linear regression analysis and the multiple regression analysis. The linear regression analysis was used in testing the individual hypothesis while the multiple regression analysis was used in testing the holistic impact of the independent variable (firm characteristics) on the dependent variable (financial reporting quality). These statistical techniques seem appropriate considering the parametric nature of the data that is generated and the nature of the research hypotheses, which are intended to measure the impact of one variable on the other. These analyses were conducted with the aid of the STATA.

Calculation of Financial Reporting Quality

This study shall use Jones (1991) model to account for discretionary component of accruals. Total Accruals (TACC) is defined as the difference between Net Income (NI) and Cash Flow from Operating Activities (OCF). i.e.

$$TACC = NI - OCF \dots \dots \dots I$$

$$TACC_{it}/A_{it-1} = \alpha_t(1/A_{it-1}) + \beta_{1i}[(\Delta REV - \Delta REC)/A_{it-1}] + \beta_{2i}[(PPE_{it})/A_{it-1}] + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots ii$$

Where:

TACC = Total Accruals (NI – OCF)

ΔREV = Change in Revenue

ΔREC = Change in Receivable

PPE = Property, Plant and Equipment

A_{it-1} = Year-end assets for company I in year t-1

ε_{it} = error term/residual

The value of earnings management is measured by the discretionary accruals. It is obtained by making the error term in the equation above the subject of the formula.

The higher the value of discretionary accrual the higher is the presence of earnings management (Hassan & Ahmed, 2012). The model for discretionary accrual is stated below by making the error term in equation 2 the subject of the formula:

$$DA = TACC_{it}/A_{it-1} - [\alpha_t(1/A_{it-1}) + \beta_{1i}[(\Delta REV - \Delta REC)/A_{it-1}] + \beta_{2i}[(PPE_{it})/A_{it-1}]]$$

On other hand, earning quality was computed using the following formula:

$$FRQ = TACC - DA$$

This relationship is as captured in the framework below.

Figure 1: Firm Characteristics Model

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization

The justification of this framework is based on the assumption that a relationship exists between firm characteristics and financial reporting quality. This implies that a change in degree of firm characteristics (that is structure, monitoring and performance) brings about a change in earning quality as proxy for financial reporting quality.

In order to estimate the relationship between firm characteristics and financial reporting quality. Financial reporting quality, which is the dependent variable, is modelled as a function of firm size, leverage, board size, institutional shareholding, profitability and liquidity. Econometrically, this is specified as:

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSZ_{it} + \beta_2 LEV_{it} + e_{it}$$

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BSZ_{it} + \beta_2 IST_{it} + e_{it}$$

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PRO_{it} + \beta_2 LIQ_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where:

FRQ	=	Financial Reporting Quality
β_0	=	Intercept
β_{1-2}	=	Coefficient of the independent variables
FSZ_{it}	=	Firm Size of firm i at time t
LEV_{it}	=	Leverage of firm i at time t
BSZ_{it}	=	Board Size of firm i at time t
IST_{it}	=	Institutional Shareholding of firm i at time t
PRO_{it}	=	Profitability of firm i at time t
LIQ_{it}	=	Liquidity of firm i at time t
e	=	error term

3.4.1 Measurement of Variables

The choice of measurement of variables in this study was made through a critical review of extant literature after which the items to be used in operationalizing the variables were established. In this study, the variables of measurement are the dependent variable and the independent variable.

While financial reporting quality is the dependent variable, firms' characteristics are the independent variable.

S/N	VARIABLE	MEASUREMENT
1	Financial Reporting Quality	The proxy to be used for financial reporting quality in this study is earnings quality and it was measured by discretionary accruals (DAC) using Jones model. However, based on prior literatures, the accrual approach to earnings quality was adopted. This is because, the estimation of the scope of earnings quality is better served with accrual models though the use of discretionary line items best used for accuracy in detection.
2	Firms' Characteristics	The components of this variable as stated in the conceptual framework are structure characteristics, monitoring characteristics, and performance characteristics.
3	Structure Characteristics	In measuring this dimension of firms' characteristics, firms' size and leverage were used as proxies. The researcher measured firms' size by the book value of the firm's total assets and leverage as ratio of debt to equity.
4	Monitoring Characteristics	Measurement of monitoring characteristics, the researcher used board size and institutional shareholding as proxies for monitoring characteristics.

		The number of board members of the firm and the total of institutional ownership measured these.
5	Performance Characteristics	The researcher using profitability and liquidity as proxies measured this dimension of firms' characteristics. These were measured by the net profit of the firm and the ratio of current asset to current liabilities.

Source: Researcher's Computation

3.5 Justification of Methods

This study makes use of descriptive research design since this study relies heavily on secondary data that are quantitative in nature and the study population had already collected these data. Secondary source of data collection were utilized because Hair, Anderson, Tatham and Black (2007) assert that some of the advantages of using secondary data are that it saves time and cost of acquiring the information generated. It is helpful to acquire the actual state of phenomenon under study.

This study utilized multiple panel regression model to examine the relationship between firm characteristics and financial reporting quality - the key variables of the study. While firms characteristics is the explanatory (predictor) variable, the dimensions are structure, monitoring, and performance; financial reporting quality, the criterion variable is measured by discretionary accruals. The use of discretionary accruals as proxy for financial reporting quality is consistent with previous studies such as Uwuigbe Daramola and Anjolaoluwa (2014). Since this study used panel

data, which is quantitative in nature, hence, analysing the data with the use of panel regression analysis is the best method because this study involves the combination of time series and cross sectional data, hence, panel regression is appropriate.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

This chapter presents the result of data analysis and tests of hypotheses formulated earlier in chapter three. First, descriptive statistics, followed by the correlation matrix table and then the

summary of Regression Result are presented and analyzed, and then discussion of findings. The data used for this study are presented in appendix A, these data are financial reporting quality (FRQ), firm size (FSZ), leverage (LEV), board size (BSZ), institutional shareholding (INS), profitability (PRO), and liquidity (LIQ).

4.2 Data Analysis and Results

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	FRQ	FSZ	LEV	BSZ	INS	PRO	LIQ
Mean	1.7296	7.2280	0.3957	9.5136	0.3307	1.0680	0.6939
Max	7.2100	11.994	3.9548	12.0000	0.70330	9.54000	1.34000

Min	0.0800	4.0606	0.0089	7.0000	0.1142	-7.8300	0.1500
Sd	1.6854	2.1135	0.3853	1.5482	0.1370	1.8480	0.3159
Skewness	1.4686	0.3986	5.1387	0.2667	0.56928	-0.3258	0.2098
Kurtosis	4.0099	2.1907	42.6646	1.8587	2.6612	9.7620	1.7744
JB	88.4424	11.830	15390.0	14.5470	12.9346	423.046	15.3833
Prob	0.0000	0.0026	0.0000	0.0006	0.0015	0.0000	0.0004
Observation	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

Source: E-view Output, 2018

Table 4.1 above indicates the rundown of the descriptive statistics. It revealed the entirety of 220 observations which comprised of 22 consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for 10 years, that from 2008-2017. The table shows the average value of financial reporting quality (FRQ) to be 1.7296 which indicates a low financial reporting quality. The minimum value of FRQ is 0.08 with maximum value of 7.21 and standard deviation of 1.6854. It indicates that the consumer goods industry in Nigeria has an average FRQ of 1.7296. The standard deviation value of 1.6854 is less than the mean value of 1.7296, it means that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean value. The skewness value of FRQ is 1.4686 which is not close to 0 and is considered to be non-symmetrical above its mean. Similarly, a maximum value of 3 for kurtosis is expected to guarantee the normal distribution (Blundell & Bond, 2000). The kurtosis value of FRQ is 4.009 which is not far above 3, it shows that the variable is normally distributed in nature.

Also, the table reveals that the average value of firm size (FSZ) is 7.228, the maximum value of 11.9942, minimum value of 4.0606, standard deviation value of 2.1135. It shows that the average value or industry value of FSZ of the consumer goods industry is 7.228. The standard deviation of the FSZ is less than the average value, it indicates that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean. The skewness value of the variable is 0.3986 which is close to zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of FSZ is 2.1907 which is close to 3, it indicates that the shape is normally distributed in nature.

The descriptive statistics reveals that leverage (LEV) mean value is 0.3957, maximum value is 3.9548, minimum value of 0.0089 and standard deviation of 0.3853. The average LEV of the consumer goods industry is 0.3957 while the highest value of LEV that can be attributed to a consumer goods company is 3.9548. The lowest value of LEV possessed by one of the consumer goods company is 0.0089. The standard deviation of 0.3853 is less than the mean value of 0.3957, it shows that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean. The skewness value of the variable is 5.1387 which is far above zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is non-symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of LEV is 42.6646 which is far above 3, it indicates that the shape is leptokurtic in nature.

The descriptive statistics exhibits the mean value of board size (BSZ) to be 9.5136, maximum value of 12, the minimum value of 7, and standard deviation value of 1.548. The average number of board members in the consumer goods industry is approximately 10, the standard deviation value of 1.5482 is less than the mean value of 9.5136 which indicates that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean. The skewness value of the variable is 0.2667 which is close to zero, it

means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of the variable is 1.8587 which is below 3, it indicates that the data is leptokurtic.

The table also indicates that the average value of institutional ownership (INS) to be 0.3307, the minimum value of INS is 0.1142 with maximum value of 0.7033 and standard deviation of 0.137. The standard deviation value of 0.137 is less than the mean value of 0.3307, it means that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean value. The skewness value of INS is 0.5692 which is close to 0 and is considered to be symmetric. Similarly, a maximum value of 3 for kurtosis is expected to guarantee the normal distribution (Blundell & Bond, 2000). The kurtosis value of INS is 2.66 which is very close to 3, it shows that the variable is normally distributed in nature.

Also, the table reveals that the average value of profitability (PRO) is 1.068, the maximum value of 9.54, minimum value of -7.83, standard deviation value of 1.848. It shows that the average value or industry value of PRO of the consumer goods industry is 1.068. The standard deviation of PRO is more than the average value; it indicates that the data are widely dispersed from the mean. The skewness value of the variable is -0.3258 which is close to zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of PRO is 9.762 which is far above 3, it indicates that the shape is leptokurtic in nature.

Likewise, liquidity (LIQ) mean value is 0.6939, maximum value is 1.34, minimum value of 0.15 and standard deviation of 0.3159. The average LIQ of the consumer goods industry is 0.6939 while the highest value of LIQ that can be attributed to a consumer goods company is 1.34. The lowest value of LIQ possessed by one of the consumer goods company is 0.15. The standard deviation of 0.3159 is less than the mean value of 0.6939, it shows that the data are not widely dispersed from

the mean. The skewness value of the variable is 0.2098 which is close to zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of LIQ is 1.7744 which is below 3, it indicates that the shape is leptokurtic in nature.

This study uses the Jarque-Bera test for normality, the results of the test indicate that are the data are not normally distributed because their P-value is less than 0.05. However, the Guasian theorem (1929) and Shao (2003) suggest that normality of data does not in any way affect the inferential statistics estimate to the BLUE.

4.2.2 Correlation Matrix

Table 4.2

VARIABLES	FSZ	LEV	BSZ	INS	PRO	LIQ
FSZ	1					
LEV	0.2064	1				

BSZ	0.5737	0.0018	1			
INS	0.0688	0.1832	-0.1070	1		
PRO	-0.1515	-0.0510	0.0008	0.1443	1	
LIQ	0.1118	0.2111	0.1599	0.2925	0.2167	1

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The table above shows the correlation values between the independent variables. The correlation matrix is used to determine the correlation between independent variables of the study. It is observed that the variables correlate fairly well (between -0.15 and 0.57). There is no correlation coefficient greater than 0.8, hence there is no problem of multicollinearity of data (Neter, Kutner, Nachtsheim & Wasserman, 1996; Cassey et. al., 1999; Wallace & Naser, 2005).

4.2.3 Variance Inflation Factor

Table 4.3

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
C	NA	0.364198

FSZ	1.683416	0.002795
LEV	1.132794	0.056582
BSZ	1.643484	0.005086
INS	1.180422	0.466461
PRO	1.112876	0.002417
LIQ	1.222983	0.090860

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The tolerance values and the variance inflation factor are two good measures of assessing multicollinearity between the independent variables in a study. The result shows that variance inflation factor were consistently smaller than ten (10) indicating complete absence of multicollinearity (Neter et al; 1996; Cassey et al., 1999). This shows the suitability of the study model been fit with the six independent variables. Also, the tolerance values were consistently smaller than 1.00, therefore extend the fact that there is complete absence of multicollinearity between the independent variables (Tobachmel & Fidell, 1996).

4.2.4 Fixed Effect Model Regression Results

Table 4.4

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	Prob
C	2.161554	0.738753	2.925950	0.0038

FSZ	-0.032793	0.100857	-0.325145	0.7454
LEV	-0.492315	0.190970	-2.577977	0.0107
R ²	0.79			
Adj. R ²	0.77			
F-Statistics	33.39333			
Prob(F-Statistics)	0.000000			
Hausman Chi2	12.283701			
Hausman Prob>Chi2	0.0022			
Heteroskedasticity Sig	0.12512			
Br-GodfreyLM Stat	15.9941			
Breusch-Godfrey Ob. R	0.3161			

Source: E-view Output, 2018

Firm Size and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line shows that $FRQ = 2.161554 - 0.032793FSZ - 0.492315LEV$ this means that financial reporting quality (FRQ) will decrease by 0.03units for every unit increase in firm size (FSZ). The significant value or P-value of FSZ is 0.7454, this significant value or P-value is more

than the t-value of 0.05, which indicates that FSZ has no significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Leverage and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line indicates that FRQ will decrease by 0.49units for every unit increase in leverage (LEV). The significant value of LEV is 0.0107, this value is less than the t-value of 0.05, Likewise, the coefficient value of LEV is negative which indicates that LEV has negative significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The F-Statistic of 33.39333 and its corresponding P-value of 0.000000 indicates that the model is fit and the independent variables are properly selected, combined and used. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.79 indicates that about 79% of variation in FRQ can be explained by FSZ and LEV or the ability of the regression line to predict FRQ is about 79%. The remaining 21% are attributed to other independent variables that are not captured in the regression. The study therefore, accepts alternate Hypothesis which states that, firm characteristics have significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The Breusch Pagan-Godfrey Test of Heteroskedasticity indicates that the probability chi-square value of 0.12512 indicates that the data are homokedasticity. Thus the p-value of 0.12512 which is greater than 0.05 makes the study to accept the null hypothesis that the residuals are not heteroskedasticity but homokedasticity and is desirable.

The Breush--Godfrey serial correlation LM test for serial correlation was performed on the residuals and the results showed observed R-squared of 0.3161, which is in excess of 0.05, which lead us to reject the presence of serial correlation in the residual.

The Hausman Specification Test indicates that Fixed Effect Model is most appropriate to Random Effect Model given the P-value of 0.0022 which is less than the critical value of 0.5.

4.2.5 Wald Test Regression Results

4.2.5.1 Structure Characteristics and Financial Reporting Quality

HO₁: Structure characteristics has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.5 Financial Reporting Quality and Firm Size

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	-0.325145	196	0.7454
F-statistic	0.105719	(1, 196)	0.7454
Chi-square	0.105719	1	0.7451

Null Hypothesis: C(1)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	-0.032793	0.100857

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

From the Wald test, it confirmed that firm size has a negative insignificant effect on financial reporting quality because the p-value is 0.7454. The intercept of -0.032793 means that, financial reporting quality will decrease by same amount for every unit increase in firm size.

Table 4.6 Financial Reporting Quality and Leverage

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	-2.577977	196	0.0107
F-statistic	6.645963	(1, 196)	0.0107
Chi-square	6.645963	1	0.0099

Null Hypothesis: C(2)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	-0.492315	0.190970

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The Wald result of the financial reporting quality and leverage indicates that financial reporting quality will decrease by -0.492315unit as leverage increases. Leverage has a negative significant effect on financial reporting quality with p-value of 0.0107.

Therefore, it is concluded that structure characteristics as measure by firm size and leverage has a significant effect on financial reporting quality of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.10 Summary Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	Prob
C	-1.771299	0.677084	-2.616070	0.0095
BSZ	0.144872	0.063288	2.289114	0.0230
IST	6.417117	0.715180	8.972732	0.0000
R ²	0.27			
Adj. R ²	0.26			
F-Statistics	41.14720			
Prob(F-Statistics)	0.000000			

Source: E-view Output, 2018

Board Size and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line reveals that FRQ will increase by 0.14 units for every unit increase in board size (BSZ). The significant value or P-value of BSZ is 0.0230, this significant value or P-value is less than the t-value of 0.05, which indicates that BSZ has significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Institutional Shareholding and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line indicates that FRQ will increase by 0.41 units for every unit increase in institutional shareholding (IST). The significant value or P-value of INS is 0.0000, this significant value or P-value is less than the t-value of 0.05, which indicates that INT has significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The F-Statistic of 41.14720 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0000 indicates that the model is fit. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.27 indicates that about 27% of variation in FRQ can be explained by BSZ and IST or the ability of the regression line to predict FRQ is about 27%. The remaining variation is attributed to other independent variables that are not captured in the regression. The study therefore, accepts alternate Hypothesis which states that, monitoring characteristics have significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

4.2.5.2 Monitoring Characteristics and Financial Reporting Quality

HO₂: Monitoring characteristics have no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.8 Financial Reporting Quality and board size

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	2.289114	217	0.0230
F-statistic	5.240041	(1, 217)	0.0230
Chi-square	5.240041	1	0.0221

Null Hypothesis: C(1)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	0.144872	0.063288

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The Wald test confirmed that board size has a positive significant effect on financial reporting quality because the p-value is 0.0230. The intercept of 0.144812 means that, financial reporting quality will increase by same amount for every unit increase in board size.

Table 4.9 Financial Reporting Quality and Institutional shareholding

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	8.972732	217	0.0000
F-statistic	80.50993	(1, 217)	0.0000
Chi-square	80.50993	1	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: C(2)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	6.417117	0.715180

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The Wald test attests that institutional shareholding has a positive significant effect on financial reporting quality because the p-value is 0.0000. The intercept of 6.417117 means that, financial reporting quality will increase by same amount for every unit increase in institutional shareholdings.

Table 4.10 Summary of Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	Prob
C	-0.292489	0.231451	-1.263721	0.2077
PRO	0.013964	0.053138	0.262780	0.7930
LIQ	2.892680	0.310779	9.307840	0.0000
R ²	0.30			
Adj. R ²	0.29			
F-Statistics	46.04593			
Prob(F-Statistics)	0.000000			

Source: E-view Output, 2018

Profitability and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line indicates that FRQ will increase by 0.0139664 units for every unit increase in profitability (PRO). The significant value or P-value of PRO is 0.7930, this significant value or P-value is more than the t-value of 0.05, which indicates that PRO has no significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Liquidity and Financial Reporting Quality

The regression line reveals that FRQ will increase by 2.89 units for every unit increase in liquidity (LIQ). The significant value or P-value of LIQ is 0.0000, this significant value or P-value is less

than the t-value of 0.05, which indicates that LIQ has significant effects on FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The F-Statistic of 46.04593 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0000 indicates that the model is fit and the independent variables are properly selected, combined and used. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.30 indicates that about 30% of variation in FRQ can be explained by PRO and LIQ or the ability of the regression line to predict FRQ is about 30%. The remaining variation is attributed to other independent variables that are not captured in the regression. The study therefore, accepts alternate Hypothesis which states that, firm characteristics have significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

4.2.5.3 Performance Characteristics and Financial Reporting Quality

H0₃: Performance characteristics have no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.11 Financial Reporting Quality and profitability

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	0.262780	217	0.7930
F-statistic	0.069054	(1, 217)	0.7930
Chi-square	0.069054	1	0.7927

Null Hypothesis: C(1)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	0.013964	0.053138

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The Wald test confirmed that profitability has a positive insignificant effect on financial reporting quality because the p-value is 0.7930. The intercept of 0.013964 means that, financial reporting quality will increase by same amount for every unit increase in profitability.

Table 4.12 Financial Reporting quality and Liquidity

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	9.307840	217	0.0000
F-statistic	86.63588	(1, 217)	0.0000
Chi-square	86.63588	1	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: C(2)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	2.892680	0.310779

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: E-view Output, 2018

The result indicates that leverage has a positive significant effect on financial reporting quality with p-value of 0.0000. Therefore, the study concluded that performance characteristics as measure by profitability and liquidity has a significant effect on financial reporting quality of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

In the regression result, firm size (FSZ) has no significant effect on financial reporting quality (FRQ) of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicates that FSZ does not influence the quality of financial reporting significantly. The coefficient of FSZ is negative which may be as a result of the fact that large firms are visible and susceptible to political attacks, in the form of pressure for the exercise of social responsibilities, greater regulation such as price control and higher corporate taxes which may make firms react by avoiding attention which disclosure of some significant facts could have brought to them. The finding is in tandem with the findings in the previous works of Missonier-Piera (2004); Thoopsamut and Jaikengkit (2009); Waweru and Riro (2013); Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016). Also, the finding is contrary to the study of Cohen (2004); Hung and Song (2006); Huang, Rose-Green and Lee (2012); Shehu (2012); Shehu and Ahmad (2013).

In the case of leverage and financial reporting quality, a significant negative effect was found. This indicates that FRQ will reduce when there is an increase in leverage. This means that increasing gearing will negatively impact on financial reporting quality. This is because the regression result indicates a negative relationship between leverage and financial reporting quality. In as much as debt financing is likely to enhance the firms' value, it is also capable of exposing the firm to the risk of liquidation or take over, managers should therefore find the optimal point for sustainable development.

This finding is consistent with the findings in previous studies such as Shehu (2013). Also, the finding is contrary to the study of Craig and Diga (1998); Klein (2002); Davidson, Stewart and

Kent (2005); Alsaeed (2006); Shehu (2012); Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017).

Based on the regression result, board size and financial reporting quality, BSZ has a significant effect on FRQ. This means that BSZ do influence FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of previous studies like Klein (2002); Shehu (2012); Joseph and Ahmed (2017); Ezelibe, Nwosu and Orazulike (2017); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017).

The regression result of institutional shareholding and financial reporting quality shows that IST does have a significant effect on FRQ. It indicates that IST influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the study of Shehu (2012); Devi and Aishah (2009); Shehu (2013).

The study found that profitability has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This means that profitability does not influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding contradicts the study of Shehu (2012).

The study also revealed that liquidity has a significant effect on financial reporting quality. This means that liquidity influences financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of Shehu (2012); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study examined the effect of firm characteristics on the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study specifically examined the effect of firm characteristics proxies by monitoring, leverage and performance, while discretionary accrual is used to proxy financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

In order to gain the advantage of an in-depth study and effective coverage, this study discussed the concept of firm characteristics and concept of financial reporting quality. This study reviewed prior literature on the subject of study and theories that are relevant for this study were discussed.

The study adopted ex-post facto research design and secondary data were collected from the annual financial reports of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Panel regression analysis was employed because the study is a time series plus cross-sectional analysis.

This study revealed that firm characteristics affects financial reporting quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. However, the study found that firm size (FSZ) has no significant effect on financial reporting quality (FRQ) of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria while leverage and financial reporting quality, a significant negative effect was found. This study also revealed that board size and financial reporting quality, BSZ has a significant effect on FRQ, while The regression result of institutional shareholding and financial reporting quality shows that IST does have a significant effect on FRQ. More so, the study revealed that liquidity has a significant effect on financial reporting quality. It is significant at five percent level and negative. The negative sign

on the coefficient suggests that institutional holding has an indirect influence on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusions

The study examined the effect of firm characteristics on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This study revealed both positive and negative findings. However, firm size (FSZ) has no significant effect on financial reporting quality (FRQ) of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicates that FSZ does not influence the quality of financial reporting significantly. The coefficient of FSZ is negative which may be as a result of the fact that large firms are visible and susceptible to political attacks, in the form of pressure for the exercise of social responsibilities, greater regulation such as price control and higher corporate taxes which may make firms react by avoiding attention which disclosure of some significant facts could have brought to them. The finding is in tandem with the findings in the previous works of Missonier-Piera (2004); Thoopsamut and Jaikengkit (2009); Waweru and Riro (2013); Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016). Also, the finding is contrary to the study of Cohen (2004); Hung and Song (2006); Huang, Rose-Green and Lee (2012); Shehu (2012); Shehu and Ahmad (2013).

Therefore, this study revealed that leverage has a significant negative influence on financial reporting quality. This indicates that FRQ will reduce when there is an increase in leverage. This means that increasing gearing will negatively impact on financial reporting quality. This is because the regression result indicates a negative relationship between leverage and financial reporting quality. In as much as debt financing is likely to enhance the firms' value, it is also capable of exposing the firm to the risk of liquidation or take over, managers should therefore find the optimal point for sustainable development. More so, this finding is consistent with the findings in previous

studies such as Shehu (2013). Also, the finding is contrary to the study of Olowokure, Muhammad and Terzungwe (2016); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017).

Based on the findings of the study, board size and financial reporting quality, BSZ has a significant effect on FRQ. This means that BSZ do influence FRQ of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of previous studies like Joseph and Ahmed (2017); Ezelibe, Nwosu and Orazulike (2017); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017). The study shows that institutional shareholding does have a significant effect on financial reporting quality. It indicates that IST influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the study of Shehu (2012); Devi and Aishah (2009); Shehu (2013).

The study found that profitability has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This means that profitability does not influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding contradicts the study of Shehu (2012). However, the study also revealed that liquidity has a significant effect on financial reporting quality. This means that liquidity influences financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of Shehu (2012); John, Nkiru and Luka (2017).

Based on the major findings as enumerated above, the following conclusions are drawn:

This study agrees that monitoring attributes can positively influence financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The study concludes that structural attributes affect financial reporting quality negatively of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The study also conclude that performance attributes has no influence on financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. This study recommends that listed consumer goods companies should strengthen their mechanisms for monitoring financial reporting quality by equipping them with the necessary information and they should be free from biasness, which will reflect in their financial reporting.
2. The study recommends that listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria should review the mechanisms that makes up the structure characteristics of their business. Because this study revealed that structure attributes influence financial reporting quality negatively by so doing the report will not be free from biasness.
3. Since performance does not reduce the quality of financial reporting of consumer goods companies in Nigeria, performance should be relative to the firm's business needs, scope and complexity. Since no two firms are exactly alike in all ramifications, it is important that an appropriate method for presenting financial reporting should be understood to be a function of each firm's circumstances. Setting arbitrary financial reporting quality

benchmarks may therefore be counterproductive because this study found that performance characteristics does not affect quality of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

This study is limited by its concentration on only listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. First of all, this research showed the effect of only six independent variables which are the firm size, firm leverage, board size, institutional shareholding, profitability and liquidity as the variables constituting the firms' characteristics. Those are the most commonly used characteristics in the prior literature testing their effect on financial reporting quality. So this could be a limitation as there might be other characteristics that can explain financial reporting quality. Another limitation of this research is that the result of this study cannot be generalized, because the research is conducted only on the 22 listed consumer goods companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSN) and not all the firms listed. The study is also limited to the period of 2008-2017.

5.5 Suggestion for Further Study

Considering the previous discussion of the major findings and the conclusion of this study, there are possible avenues that can be explored in future research.

This work is limited to listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria; it is recommended that a similar study can be extended to other sectors of the economy. Future research could consider other firm characteristics rather than those used in this study and other independent variables like corporate governance variables and cultural dimensions that might have a greater impact on the dependent variable (financial reporting quality, measured by the discretionary accruals). Interested researcher can also extend the scope of the study as this study only covered 2008-2017.

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Appendix A: Data Presentation

COMPANY	YEAR	ID	FRQ	FSZ	LEV	BSZ	INS	PRO	LIQ
7up Bottling Company PLC	2008	1	1.61	8.0733	1.2423	9	0.1236	1.25	1.03

	2009	1	1.42	7.0722	1.1701	9	0.5384	1.18	0.76
	2010	1	2.29	7.0775	1.0629	9	0.5382	1.29	0.94
	2011	1	4.51	8.0711	0.9809	9	0.5416	1.32	1.01
	2012	1	4.26	7.0733	1.2423	9	0.5409	0.61	1.18
	2013	1	4.91	7.6456	0.5552	8	0.6826	1.37	1.22
	2014	1	6.56	8.0733	0.4567	9	0.6959	0.38	1.14
	2015	1	4.45	8.0213	0.5588	9	0.7033	0.39	1.16
	2016	1	5.89	8.0761	0.0705	9	0.6447	0.42	1.12
	2017	1	4.87	7.0785	0.0614	9	0.5022	1.85	1.21
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2008	2	4.63	9.0987	0.0427	11	0.4311	1.52	1.19
	2009	2	4.41	9.0543	0.0238	10	0.4832	0.63	0.98
	2010	2	5.71	9.0213	0.1815	10	0.5541	1.38	1.05
	2011	2	6.11	8.0876	0.3381	11	0.6253	0.94	1.21
	2012	2	3.04	8.0561	0.1424	11	0.5555	2.57	1.07
	2013	2	2.71	9.7312	0.1022	10	0.6666	2.04	1.25
	2014	2	4.81	8.4021	0.4881	11	0.6253	2.05	1.03
	2015	2	5.45	8.5812	0.5644	11	0.6231	2.54	0.76
	2016	2	5.71	9.1768	0.5356	11	0.5004	2.81	0.94
	2017	2	4.09	9.0511	0.6261	10	0.6305	2.21	1.01
Champion Brewery PLC	2008	3	1.61	7.5141	0.3089	8	0.4444	2.05	1.18
	2009	3	2.23	7.2172	2.9192	8	0.6347	1.26	1.22
	2010	3	2.51	7.0955	3.9548	8	0.4926	0.22	1.14
	2011	3	2.72	7.2214	0.2296	8	0.3531	1.95	1.16
	2012	3	3.81	7.1842	1.2707	7	0.2376	1.88	1.01
	2013	3	5.61	7.1842	1.1893	8	0.2416	1.88	1.22

	2014	3	4.62	7.1387	0.5751	8	0.3348	1.32	1.14
	2015	3	6.11	7.0185	0.3751	8	0.4058	0.32	0.91
	2016	3	5.71	6.8545	1.0573	8	0.3012	2.66	1.16
	2017	3	6.64	6.7999	1.2611	8	0.4994	2.16	1.07
Dangote Flour Mills PLC	2008	4	4.14	7.3214	0.3059	11	0.3273	2.49	1.04
	2009	4	4.11	7.6594	0.5015	12	0.2977	0.28	0.95
	2010	4	4.54	7.6889	0.0555	12	0.2417	1.27	0.84
	2011	4	5.96	7.7584	0.0246	12	0.2101	0.35	0.98
	2012	4	6.91	7.5066	0.0634	12	0.3107	1.99	1.11
	2013	4	7.21	7.4023	0.2663	12	0.2296	0.71	1.01
	2014	4	4.43	7.2911	0.3217	12	0.3143	1.16	1.04
	2015	4	3.88	7.2543	0.2832	12	0.3723	1.13	1.03
	2016	4	2.89	7.0218	0.0089	11	0.3265	2.82	0.76
	2017	4	2.32	7.1275	0.0098	11	0.4528	2.26	0.94
Dongote Sugar Refinery PLC	2008	5	2.29	9.9453	0.1537	10	0.5623	2.39	0.79
	2009	5	1.17	10.823	0.3054	10	0.5793	0.23	0.91
	2010	5	4.17	9.8756	0.3578	9	0.5218	1.45	1.14
	2011	5	2.86	9.4897	0.0287	9	0.4893	0.65	0.76
	2012	5	3.91	9.0781	0.0107	10	0.5462	2.37	0.66
	2013	5	4.49	9.8793	0.6578	10	0.5137	1.82	1.12
	2014	5	4.57	8.3786	0.8745	10	0.4971	1.91	0.81
	2015	5	4.77	8.2664	0.7334	10	0.4286	0.36	0.73
	2016	5	3.91	9.7214	0.6552	10	0.4728	2.66	0.68
	2017	5	3.05	9.5482	0.1926	10	0.4025	2.26	0.66
DN Tyre & Rubber PLC	2008	6	3.15	6.5463	0.4976	8	0.4261	3.23	0.61

	2009	6	3.64	6.5551	0.3058	8	0.4286	0.12	0.35
	2010	6	4.22	6.4724	0.4772	8	0.5456	1.47	0.83
	2011	6	4.96	6.3613	0.3125	8	0.5038	1.54	0.73
	2012	6	4.86	6.4172	0.3132	7	0.3479	1.66	0.63
	2013	6	4.82	6.3775	0.2165	8	0.3817	1.59	0.81
	2014	6	3.64	6.3722	0.2571	8	0.4231	1.89	0.89
	2015	6	2.23	5.1731	0.2474	8	0.3591	0.41	1.08
	2016	6	2.29	5.1184	0.3068	8	0.3819	2.69	1.23
	2017	6	2.32	6.6523	0.3251	8	0.3192	2.71	1.11
Flour Mills Nigeria PLC	2008	7	1.99	5.3211	0.1591	9	0.4113	3.11	1.03
	2009	7	1.02	5.3441	0.1939	9	0.3012	2.68	1.11
	2010	7	1.05	5.1987	0.2312	9	0.4092	3.33	1.04
	2011	7	1.22	5.0987	0.1732	9	0.4842	3.09	1.08
	2012	7	1.56	5.1287	0.3921	9	0.4231	4.51	1.07
	2013	7	1.88	5.0365	0.4123	9	0.4213	4.28	1.11
	2014	7	1.55	4.8976	0.3521	9	0.5723	4.63	1.06
	2015	7	1.72	4.7342	0.1714	9	0.4972	3.94	1.19
	2016	7	1.13	4.8698	0.1879	9	0.5243	1.13	1.21
	2017	7	1.17	5.0453	0.2656	8	0.4587	1.28	1.34
Golden Guinea Brewery PLC	2008	8	2.72	4.7598	0.1335	11	0.2921	1.12	1.24
	2009	8	0.64	5.0321	0.3145	11	0.2993	0.02	1.28
	2010	8	0.66	4.8564	0.1867	12	0.2937	1.48	0.95
	2011	8	0.92	4.6123	0.1735	12	0.1723	0.29	0.97
	2012	8	0.88	4.8234	0.2497	12	0.1193	1.18	0.93
	2013	8	0.72	4.4237	0.4332	12	0.1825	1.43	0.95

	2014	8	0.92	4.7476	0.1101	12	0.1341	0.69	0.96
	2015	8	0.96	5.8876	0.3122	12	0.2175	3.41	0.91
	2016	8	0.88	5.7345	0.2641	12	0.1533	3.52	1.09
	2017	8	0.76	5.5634	0.2816	12	0.1142	3.63	0.98
Guinness NigPlc	2008	9	1.89	8.7646	0.1945	11	0.2062	4.44	1.09
	2009	9	1.53	9.0953	0.3619	11	0.1172	3.13	1.15
	2010	9	1.17	9.7623	0.2313	11	0.1499	2.46	1.12
	2011	9	0.57	8.6543	0.2816	11	0.1809	1.21	1.16
	2012	9	0.35	8.0976	0.4641	10	0.2901	1.51	1.12
	2013	9	0.31	9.2167	0.4818	11	0.2321	3.12	1.11
	2014	9	0.19	9.7845	0.3527	11	0.1428	3.39	1.13
	2015	9	0.12	8.2197	0.2921	11	0.1715	2.01	1.12
	2016	9	0.13	9.0853	0.3655	11	0.1631	0.96	0.29
	2017	9	0.11	8.9845	0.2955	11	0.1175	1.51	0.21
HoneyWell Flour Mill Plc	2008	10	0.08	4.7598	0.1743	9	0.2773	3.01	0.31
	2009	10	0.11	4.8534	0.1262	9	0.2381	4.92	0.34
	2010	10	0.52	4.6123	0.5272	9	0.3023	2.16	0.53
	2011	10	0.13	4.8246	0.5619	9	0.2903	1.49	0.55
	2012	10	0.21	4.4231	0.5493	9	0.2562	1.31	0.47
	2013	10	0.35	4.7498	0.5931	9	0.2763	1.28	0.51
	2014	10	0.64	5.0342	0.5931	9	0.2846	1.09	0.48
	2015	10	0.66	5.8032	0.5272	8	0.3214	1.29	0.56
	2016	10	0.83	4.5897	0.5459	9	0.3745	2.32	0.55
	2017	10	0.49	5.8954	0.5868	9	0.4857	2.68	0.31
International Brew.Plc	2008	11	0.38	4.3287	0.1754	9	0.4166	-0.23	0.31

	2009	11	0.31	4.5783	0.1281	9	0.4254	9.54	0.22
	2010	11	0.18	4.6087	0.1401	9	0.3515	-7.83	0.27
	2011	11	0.14	4.0791	0.1088	9	0.3174	0.71	0.31
	2012	11	0.15	4.0653	0.2119	8	0.2374	0.61	0.29
	2013	11	0.88	4.2308	0.2175	9	0.3114	2.63	0.21
	2014	11	0.84	4.1378	0.2008	9	0.2541	1.33	0.31
	2015	11	0.81	4.1761	0.1451	9	0.2705	1.31	0.34
	2016	11	0.72	4.3424	0.1353	9	0.2592	2.11	0.53
	2017	11	0.76	4.3424	0.1408	9	0.3263	2.76	0.55
McnicholsPlc	2008	12	0.66	5.3867	0.3604	8	0.2484	0.17	0.47
	2009	12	0.56	5.1076	0.3562	8	0.2557	0.04	0.51
	2010	12	0.48	4.6089	0.4911	8	0.2031	-0.49	0.53
	2011	12	0.92	5.7854	0.5424	8	0.3846	2.47	0.55
	2012	12	0.72	5.9856	0.4545	7	0.3627	1.76	0.47
	2013	12	0.64	6.0986	0.3339	8	0.3743	1.73	0.51
	2014	12	0.52	6.9976	0.5999	8	0.2346	2.17	0.65
	2015	12	0.64	6.8876	0.4027	8	0.3636	1.05	0.65
	2016	12	0.88	6.8135	0.4911	8	0.4873	0.35	0.61
	2017	12	0.72	6.8797	0.4341	8	0.5217	-3.72	0.58
Multi-Trex Integrated Foods Plc	2008	13	0.56	4.0653	0.2131	7	0.2934	-6.43	0.38
	2009	13	0.84	4.1768	0.2522	7	0.3123	4.78	0.46
	2010	13	0.88	4.3238	0.1238	7	0.2046	1.03	0.49
	2011	13	0.65	4.5763	0.2214	7	0.2702	1.81	0.53
	2012	13	0.68	5.2871	0.2614	7	0.1247	-5.59	0.55
	2013	13	0.85	5.4532	0.2214	7	0.1177	2.59	0.51

	2014	13	0.84	5.9231	0.1385	7	0.2885	1.06	0.53
	2015	13	0.96	6.4421	0.2817	7	0.3281	-5.51	0.57
	2016	13	0.54	6.5532	0.1258	7	0.2591	1.83	0.26
	2017	13	0.48	6.7187	0.2778	7	0.2484	-0.64	0.31
Nig Flour Mills Plc	2008	14	0.89	4.2041	0.3428	9	0.3854	-3.83	0.35
	2009	14	0.85	4.1461	0.3203	9	0.2374	8.68	0.39
	2010	14	0.89	4.2442	0.3654	9	0.2031	-1.97	0.32
	2011	14	0.83	4.3178	0.3637	9	0.3273	-2.06	0.38
	2012	14	0.85	4.5442	0.2826	9	0.2842	0.55	0.36
	2013	14	0.66	4.7323	0.3612	9	0.2969	0.62	0.33
	2014	14	0.63	4.0606	0.2317	9	0.1821	0.59	0.22
	2015	14	0.98	4.2788	0.2653	9	0.2446	1.88	0.28
	2016	14	0.78	5.1943	0.1477	9	0.3333	1.93	0.26
	2017	14	0.49	5.2789	0.2475	9	0.4242	2.91	0.15
Nascon Allied industries Plc	2008	15	0.11	5.6745	0.1109	8	0.3821	1.24	0.17
	2009	15	0.17	5.4302	0.1626	8	0.4632	2.44	0.21
	2010	15	0.69	6.3089	0.1243	8	0.3829	2.52	0.18
	2011	15	0.86	6.2167	0.1132	8	0.3952	4.71	0.31
	2012	15	0.54	6.1973	0.2109	8	0.2561	3.62	0.33
	2013	15	0.53	6.4433	0.1609	7	0.2762	2.65	0.24
	2014	15	0.83	6.8782	0.1178	8	0.3586	2.64	0.28
	2015	15	0.87	5.6534	0.1264	8	0.3743	0.31	0.31
	2016	15	0.83	6.5345	0.1653	8	0.2346	0.79	0.34
	2017	15	0.24	6.7564	0.2187	8	0.3572	0.03	0.38
Nestle Nig. Plc	2008	16	0.91	8.1876	0.3604	11	0.3827	0.22	0.34

	2009	16	0.87	8.1876	0.3987	11	0.5342	0.11	0.16
	2010	16	0.59	8.9864	0.3572	11	0.4432	0.26	0.33
	2011	16	1.36	9.7123	0.3987	10	0.3593	0.31	0.36
	2012	16	1.49	8.2664	0.4396	11	0.3858	0.21	0.34
	2013	16	1.75	9.1984	0.4911	11	0.3334	0.11	0.48
	2014	16	0.63	8.7234	0.4396	11	0.3222	0.16	0.51
	2015	16	1.21	9.2652	0.3183	11	0.4682	0.11	0.71
	2016	16	1.22	9.3907	0.3604	11	0.3107	0.12	0.57
	2017	16	0.91	9.3242	0.3685	11	0.3675	0.13	0.51
Nigeria Brew Plc	2008	17	0.51	10.321	0.5879	12	0.4218	0.03	0.62
	2009	17	1.36	10.472	0.6307	12	0.3319	0.01	0.57
	2010	17	1.42	11.934	0.5999	12	0.3456	0.05	0.61
	2011	17	1.42	11.523	0.5424	12	0.4563	0.09	0.58
	2012	17	1.31	10.589	0.5871	11	0.4286	0.21	0.45
	2013	17	1.34	10.379	0.5017	12	0.3787	0.04	0.44
	2014	17	1.33	10.646	0.5462	12	0.43201	0.03	0.52
	2015	17	1.28	10.652	0.6464	12	0.4141	0.06	0.47
	2016	17	0.88	9.7823	0.6739	12	0.3951	0.02	0.47
	2017	17	0.94	9.8926	0.5272	12	0.3804	0.06	0.52
Nigeria Enamelware Plc	2008	18	0.86	6.2546	0.0667	9	0.1749	0.01	0.47
	2009	18	0.98	6.8432	0.0397	9	0.1943	0.02	0.45
	2010	18	0.69	7.2647	0.0417	9	0.2017	0.02	0.48
	2011	18	0.92	7.5579	0.0158	9	0.2073	0.01	0.49
	2012	18	1.27	7.6521	0.0212	9	0.2065	0.03	0.47
	2013	18	1.14	7.6272	0.0249	8	0.1634	0.05	0.51

	2014	18	1.12	6.8753	0.0133	9	0.1429	0.04	0.31
	2015	18	0.72	6.8001	0.0189	9	0.1445	0.05	0.36
	2016	18	0.83	6.8434	0.0265	9	0.2468	0.03	0.31
	2017	18	1.27	6.3216	0.0138	9	0.1833	0.03	0.45
PZ Cussons Nig. Plc	2008	19	1.04	11.153	0.4882	11	0.1766	0.03	0.78
	2009	19	1.38	10.589	0.4118	11	0.1752	0.08	0.76
	2010	19	0.77	11.267	0.5661	11	0.1589	0.06	0.66
	2011	19	0.98	10.378	0.5972	11	0.1625	0.01	0.68
	2012	19	0.83	10.415	0.6541	11	0.1598	0.26	0.81
	2013	19	1.32	11.994	0.5598	10	0.2103	0.03	0.81
	2014	19	1.21	11.619	0.5272	11	0.3112	0.03	0.63
	2015	19	1.15	10.266	0.5198	11	0.2022	0.01	0.42
	2016	19	1.02	11.275	0.5341	11	0.2218	0.01	0.45
	2017	19	1.01	10.987	0.4871	11	0.1598	0.15	0.34
Unilever Nig. Plc	2008	20	1.11	11.188	0.6531	12	0.1833	0.01	0.41
	2009	20	1.04	10.412	0.6525	12	0.1752	0.05	0.43
	2010	20	1.03	10.612	0.5343	12	0.1974	0.04	0.31
	2011	20	1.11	11.2	0.6734	12	0.1846	0.02	0.36
	2012	20	1.14	10.056	0.6401	11	0.2218	0.04	0.31
	2013	20	0.27	11.468	0.5587	12	0.2071	0.01	0.45
	2014	20	0.54	11.945	0.6683	12	0.2154	0.12	0.78
	2015	20	0.53	10.821	0.6809	12	0.3012	0.15	0.76
	2016	20	0.81	10.762	0.5025	12	0.2103	0.05	0.66
	2017	20	0.79	10.629	0.5972	12	0.2205	0.06	0.68
Union Dicon Salt Plc	2008	21	0.61	5.9823	0.3483	9	0.2113	0.04	0.78

	2009	21	0.76	5.0023	0.3478	9	0.2334	0.14	0.76
	2010	21	0.54	6.0982	0.3365	9	0.3269	0.06	0.66
	2011	21	0.63	6.2987	0.4213	9	0.1499	0.02	0.68
	2012	21	0.65	7.0823	0.3505	9	0.1173	0.05	0.93
	2013	21	0.75	7.2354	0.3875	9	0.2773	0.05	0.87
	2014	21	0.45	6.9845	0.3062	8	0.2668	0.08	0.82
	2015	21	0.56	6.0654	0.4217	9	0.1569	0.07	0.74
	2016	21	0.69	6.9821	0.3715	9	0.1867	0.05	0.66
	2017	21	0.87	6.4521	0.4576	9	0.1499	0.05	0.69
Vitafoam	2008	22	0.63	7.8915	0.2243	8	0.2127	0.04	0.68
	2009	22	0.78	7.2546	0.3868	8	0.2913	0.02	0.75
	2010	22	0.54	6.9826	0.3509	8	0.2767	0.01	0.76
	2011	22	0.53	7.9234	0.2576	8	0.3187	0.04	0.71
	2012	22	0.65	6.9264	0.3534	8	0.2189	0.07	0.73
	2013	22	0.76	6.3764	0.3154	8	0.3348	0.09	0.78
	2014	22	1.37	6.2176	0.3932	7	0.2313	0.03	0.38
	2015	22	1.23	6.9864	0.3703	8	0.2884	0.08	0.41
	2016	22	0.97	6.3784	0.3941	8	0.2774	0.05	0.47
	2017	22	0.78	7.3276	0.3217	8	0.2587	0.07	0.49

Appendix B: Descriptive Statistics

	FRQ	FSZ	LEV	BSZ	INS	PRO	LIQ
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Mean	1.729682	7.228062	0.395766	9.513636	0.330790	1.068045	0.693909
Median	0.950000	6.985450	0.345300	9.000000	0.311300	0.865000	0.660000
Maximum	7.210000	11.99420	3.954800	12.00000	0.703300	9.540000	1.340000
Minimum	0.080000	4.060600	0.008900	7.000000	0.114200	-7.830000	0.150000
Std. Dev.	1.685400	2.113534	0.385361	1.548249	0.137007	1.848000	0.315978
Skewness	1.468698	0.398652	5.138726	0.266703	0.569283	-0.325832	0.209816
Kurtosis	4.009935	2.190716	42.66469	1.858760	2.661296	9.762088	1.774401
Jarque-Bera	88.44240	11.83082	15390.04	14.54704	12.93464	423.0462	15.38335
Probability	0.000000	0.002698	0.000000	0.000694	0.001553	0.000000	0.000457
Sum	380.5300	1590.174	87.06860	2093.000	72.77381	234.9700	152.6600
Sum Sq. Dev.	622.0857	978.2784	32.52212	524.9591	4.110845	747.9075	21.86544
Observations	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

Appendix C

FIRST MODEL

POOLED REGRESSION

Dependent Variable: FRQ

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:40

Sample: 2008 2017

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 22

Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FSZ	0.127139	0.054076	2.351099	0.0196
LEV	0.479072	0.296583	1.615304	0.1077
C	0.621116	0.400080	1.552482	0.1220

R-squared	0.044627	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.035822	S.D. dependent var	1.685400
S.E. of regression	1.654938	Akaike info criterion	3.858946

Sum squared resid	594.3238	Schwarz criterion	3.905223
Log likelihood	-421.4841	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.877634
F-statistic	5.068228	Durbin-Watson stat	0.192483
Prob(F-statistic)	0.007059		

Appendix D

FIXED EFFECT

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:34
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FSZ	-0.032793	0.100857	-0.325145	0.7454
LEV	-0.492315	0.190970	-2.577977	0.0107
C	2.161554	0.738753	2.925950	0.0038

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.796690	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.772833	S.D. dependent var	1.685400
S.E. of regression	0.803297	Akaike info criterion	2.502484
Sum squared resid	126.4760	Schwarz criterion	2.872698
Log likelihood	-251.2733	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.651986
F-statistic	33.39333	Durbin-Watson stat	1.020901
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Appendix E

RANDOM MODEL

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:36
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FSZ	0.127139	0.054076	2.351099	0.0196
LEV	0.479072	0.296583	1.615304	0.1077
C	0.621116	0.400080	1.552482	0.1220

R-squared	0.044627	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.035822	S.D. dependent var	1.685400

S.E. of regression	1.654938	Akaike info criterion	3.858946
Sum squared resid	594.3238	Schwarz criterion	3.905223
Log likelihood	-421.4841	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.877634
F-statistic	5.068228	Durbin-Watson stat	0.192483
Prob(F-statistic)	0.007059		

Appendix F

HAUSMAN SPECIFICATION

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	12.283701	2	0.0022

Cross-section random effects test comparisons:

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
FSZ	-0.032793	0.028845	0.002980	0.2589
LEV	-0.492315	-0.431214	0.000934	0.0456

Cross-section random effects test equation:

Dependent Variable: FRQ

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:37

Sample: 2008 2017

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 22

Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.161554	0.738753	2.925950	0.0038
FSZ	-0.032793	0.100857	-0.325145	0.7454
LEV	-0.492315	0.190970	-2.577977	0.0107

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.796690	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.772833	S.D. dependent var	1.685400
S.E. of regression	0.803297	Akaike info criterion	2.502484
Sum squared resid	126.4760	Schwarz criterion	2.872698
Log likelihood	-251.2733	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.651986
F-statistic	33.39333	Durbin-Watson stat	1.020901
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Appendix G

WALD TEST

FRQ AND FSZ

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	-0.325145	196	0.7454
F-statistic	0.105719	(1, 196)	0.7454
Chi-square	0.105719	1	0.7451

Null Hypothesis: $C(1)=0$

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	-0.032793	0.100857

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix H

FRQ AND LEV

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	-2.577977	196	0.0107
F-statistic	6.645963	(1, 196)	0.0107
Chi-square	6.645963	1	0.0099

Null Hypothesis: $C(2)=0$

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	-0.492315	0.190970

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix I

SECOND MODEL

POOLED REGRESSION

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:57
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BSZ	0.144872	0.063288	2.289114	0.0230
IST	6.417117	0.715180	8.972732	0.0000
C	-1.771299	0.677084	-2.616070	0.0095
R-squared	0.274961	Mean dependent var		1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.268279	S.D. dependent var		1.685400
S.E. of regression	1.441703	Akaike info criterion		3.583070
Sum squared resid	451.0361	Schwarz criterion		3.629346
Log likelihood	-391.1377	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.601757
F-statistic	41.14720	Durbin-Watson stat		0.375603
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Appendix J

FIXED EFFECT MODEL

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:06
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BSZ	0.114034	0.174009	0.655333	0.5130
IST	0.230051	0.749531	0.306926	0.7592
C	0.568709	1.692613	0.335995	0.7372

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.790290	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.765681	S.D. dependent var	1.685400
S.E. of regression	0.815844	Akaike info criterion	2.533481
Sum squared resid	130.4578	Schwarz criterion	2.903695

Log likelihood	-254.6829	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.682983
F-statistic	32.11403	Durbin-Watson stat	0.897744
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Appendix K

RANDOM MODEL

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:07
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220
Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BSZ	0.110643	0.119467	0.926138	0.3554
IST	1.162580	0.708109	1.641810	0.1021
C	0.292492	1.203516	0.243031	0.8082

Effects Specification

	S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random	1.132569	0.6584
Idiosyncratic random	0.815844	0.3416

Weighted Statistics

R-squared	0.014347	Mean dependent var	0.384170
Adjusted R-squared	0.005262	S.D. dependent var	0.841353
S.E. of regression	0.839136	Sum squared resid	152.8003
F-statistic	1.579268	Durbin-Watson stat	0.751071
Prob(F-statistic)	0.208486		

Unweighted Statistics

R-squared	0.094397	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Sum squared resid	563.3626	Durbin-Watson stat	0.196241

Appendix L

HAUSMAN SPECIFICATION

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test
Equation: Untitled
Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	14.567498	2	0.0007

Cross-section random effects test comparisons:

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
BSZ	0.114034	0.110643	0.016007	0.9786
IST	0.230051	1.162580	0.060379	0.0001

Cross-section random effects test equation:

Dependent Variable: FRQ

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:08

Sample: 2008 2017

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 22

Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.568709	1.692613	0.335995	0.7372
BSZ	0.114034	0.174009	0.655333	0.5130
IST	0.230051	0.749531	0.306926	0.7592

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.790290	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.765681	S.D. dependent var	1.685400
S.E. of regression	0.815844	Akaike info criterion	2.533481
Sum squared resid	130.4578	Schwarz criterion	2.903695
Log likelihood	-254.6829	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.682983
F-statistic	32.11403	Durbin-Watson stat	0.897744
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Appendix M

WALD TEST

FRQ AND BSZ

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	2.289114	217	0.0230
F-statistic	5.240041	(1, 217)	0.0230
Chi-square	5.240041	1	0.0221

Null Hypothesis: C(1)=0
 Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	0.144872	0.063288

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix N

FRQ AND IST

Wald Test:
 Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	8.972732	217	0.0000
F-statistic	80.50993	(1, 217)	0.0000
Chi-square	80.50993	1	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: C(2)=0
 Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	6.417117	0.715180

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix O

THIRD MODEL

Pooled Regression

Dependent Variable: FRQ
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:46
 Sample: 2008 2017
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 22
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PRO	0.013964	0.053138	0.262780	0.7930

LIQ	2.892680	0.310779	9.307840	0.0000
C	-0.292489	0.231451	-1.263721	0.2077
R-squared	0.297943	Mean dependent var		1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.291473	S.D. dependent var		1.685400
S.E. of regression	1.418670	Akaike info criterion		3.550859
Sum squared resid	436.7394	Schwarz criterion		3.597136
Log likelihood	-387.5945	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.569547
F-statistic	46.04593	Durbin-Watson stat		0.326273
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Appendix P

FIXED EFFECT MODEL

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:50
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PRO	0.000573	0.035006	0.016377	0.9870
LIQ	0.220607	0.380801	0.579325	0.5630
C	1.575988	0.273112	5.770474	0.0000

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.790117	Mean dependent var		1.729682
Adjusted R-squared	0.765488	S.D. dependent var		1.685400
S.E. of regression	0.816179	Akaike info criterion		2.534302
Sum squared resid	130.5650	Schwarz criterion		2.904516
Log likelihood	-254.7732	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.683804
F-statistic	32.08067	Durbin-Watson stat		0.907097
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Appendix Q

RANDOM MODEL

Dependent Variable: FRQ
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 17:51
Sample: 2008 2017
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 22
Total panel (balanced) observations: 220
Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PRO	0.007398	0.034690	0.213261	0.8313
LIQ	0.741224	0.350402	2.115356	0.0355
C	1.207438	0.351101	3.439006	0.0007

Effects Specification		S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random		1.148136	0.6643
Idiosyncratic random		0.816179	0.3357

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.019537	Mean dependent var	0.379361
Adjusted R-squared	0.010501	S.D. dependent var	0.839715
S.E. of regression	0.835294	Sum squared resid	151.4045
F-statistic	2.162053	Durbin-Watson stat	0.774171
Prob(F-statistic)	0.117561		

Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.133938	Mean dependent var	1.729682
Sum squared resid	538.7647	Durbin-Watson stat	0.207760

Appendix R

WALD TEST

FRQ AND PRO

Wald Test:
Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	0.262780	217	0.7930
F-statistic	0.069054	(1, 217)	0.7930
Chi-square	0.069054	1	0.7927

Null Hypothesis: C(1)=0
Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	0.013964	0.053138

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix S

FRQ AND LIQ

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	9.307840	217	0.0000
F-statistic	86.63588	(1, 217)	0.0000
Chi-square	86.63588	1	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: C(2)=0

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(2)	2.892680	0.310779

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Appendix T

Appendix F: Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	6.280574	Prob. F(6,213)	0.3921
Obs*R-squared	3.307102	Prob. Chi-Square(6)	0.1252
Scaled explained SS	6.602672	Prob. Chi-Square(6)	0.3816

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID^2

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:32

Sample: 1 220

Included observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.163571	1.406778	-1.537962	0.1255
FSZ	-0.053302	0.123247	-0.432478	0.6658
LEV	-0.356029	0.554495	-0.642078	0.5215
BSZ	0.136252	0.166238	0.819618	0.4134
INS	1.252877	1.592079	0.786944	0.4322
PRO	-0.030088	0.114607	-0.262530	0.7932
LIQ	3.723773	0.702656	5.299570	0.0000

R-squared	0.150323	Mean dependent var	1.572774
Adjusted R-squared	0.126388	S.D. dependent var	3.178720
S.E. of regression	2.971061	Akaike info criterion	5.047016

Sum squared resid	1880.194	Schwarz criterion	5.154995
Log likelihood	-548.1718	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.090621
F-statistic	6.280574	Durbin-Watson stat	0.876111
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000004		

Appendix U

Appendix G: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	15.29964	Prob. F(2,211)	0.4214
Obs*R-squared	13.21015	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.3161

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:34

Sample: 1 220

Included observations: 220

Presample missing value lagged residuals set to zero.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.410065	0.389174	1.053680	0.2932
FSZ	-0.013770	0.033946	-0.405633	0.6854
LEV	0.272514	0.154074	1.768725	0.0784
BSZ	-0.009576	0.045782	-0.209172	0.8345
INS	-0.580840	0.443551	-1.309522	0.1918
PRO	-0.012193	0.031632	-0.385478	0.7003
LIQ	-0.177088	0.194356	-0.911154	0.3633
RESID(-1)	0.744414	0.068109	10.92979	0.0000
RESID(-2)	0.042972	0.069085	0.622020	0.5346

R-squared	0.591870	Mean dependent var	3.53E-16
Adjusted R-squared	0.576396	S.D. dependent var	1.256963
S.E. of regression	0.818092	Akaike info criterion	2.476366
Sum squared resid	141.2170	Schwarz criterion	2.615196
Log likelihood	-263.4002	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.532429
F-statistic	38.24909	Durbin-Watson stat	1.933142
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Appendix V

Appendix H: Variance Inflation Factor

Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 10/27/18 Time: 18:35

Sample: 1 220

Included observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
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C	0.364198	49.32318	NA
FSZ	0.002795	21.46202	1.683416
LEV	0.056582	2.333046	1.132794
BSZ	0.005086	63.98190	1.643484
INS	0.466461	8.092897	1.180422
PRO	0.002417	1.486299	1.112876
LIQ	0.090860	7.148006	1.222983
